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**A numerical and analytical analysis of
the optimization landscape of the
spherical constrained random
least-square problem**

A Dissertation submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements
for the degree of Master of Science

by

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Abstract

The knowledge of loss surface geometry and topology of an optimization problem enhances the optimization process and enables post-optimization comparison of different search algorithms. This dissertation aims to computationally reproduce analytically derived results for a random version of the spherical constrained least square minimization problem. The optimization aims to find the best approximate solution of a system of M linear equations in N unknowns: $(a_k, x) = b_k$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, M$ on the sphere $|x|^2 = N$. The random version pertains to treating the N -component vectors a_k and parameters b_k as independent and identically distributed real Gaussian random variables with mean zero. The minimization problem is examined through the lens of the statistical mechanics framework, and, the Kac-Rice formulation integrated with Random Matrix Theory (RMT) for the Wishart ensemble, for arriving at analytical results in the asymptotic limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$ at finite $\alpha = \frac{M}{N}$. The statistical mechanics approach facilitates the derivation of expected normalized minimal cost $e_{min} = \frac{\langle \epsilon_{min} \rangle}{N}$ and the large deviation function for the density of e_{min} in the asymptotic limit ($N \gg 1$). Further, it also reveals the compatibility threshold $\alpha_c < 1$, the value of α beyond which a large random linear system becomes typically incompatible on the N -sphere. The RMT-based approach allows retrieval of the large deviation function for the density of the smallest lagrange multiplier λ_{min} and gives the prediction for the asymptotic mean minimal value of the cost e_{min} at $\alpha = \frac{M}{N} > 1$. For the replication of these findings computationally, the method of Riemannian optimization is employed for simulating a solution at many random instances of the minimization problem. Finally, the enhancement of optimization by leveraging the knowledge of the optimization landscape through strategies during the process of minimization using gradient descent, simulated annealing, and neural networks is discussed, and, a post-optimization comparison of large deviation function for the minimal cost is presented.

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Introduction and Background

The focal point of this thesis is to analyze a random version of a minimization problem of least-square cost function over the sphere [23], $x^2 = N$, where $x \in R^N$. The $N \times 1$ matrix or vector x satisfying spherical constraint is to be solved for by minimization of the following cost function of least square type:

$$H(x) = \frac{\|Ax - b\|^2}{2} \quad (1.1)$$

where $A \in R^{MN}$ is an $M \times N$ real matrix, and $b \in R^M$ is an $M \times 1$ real matrix.

The initial inspiration to investigate the question formulated above stemmed from the field of statistics known as multiple factor analysis [47]. A generalization of the above problem also arises in communication theory for the reconstruction of a source signal from its encrypted form corrupted by noise when passed from a sender to a recipient [2]. The concept of the associated random landscape paradigm has its roots in the theory of disordered systems, particularly in phenomena like spin glasses, [13]. The goal is usually to find the lowest energy of the simplest spherical spin glass in a random magnetic field, and, the application of such random landscape frameworks has extended into fields such as machine learning/deep neural networks[5][14][4].

In the multiple factor analysis, known as the Procrustes problem, the aim is to find an $N \times N$ matrix X , with columns of unit norm, such that A is mapped to B ($B = AX$) with maximal precision. Here the matrices A and B are $M \times N$ dimensional with $M > N$. In such over-complete systems, the exact solution of x can not be found but an approximate solution can be sought. In seeking an approximate solution, the typical approach is to minimize a cost function that penalizes deviations from the relationship ($B = AX$). For each column of x and the corresponding column of B , a solution for the respective column of x that minimizes the deviation can be searched while adhering to the unit norm constraint for each column of x . In this context, least square fitting stands out as one of the most commonly employed minimization techniques [49][10].

However the optimization problem under consideration involves finding $N \times 1$ matrix or vector x , satisfying spherical constraint, that minimizes the least square cost function 1.1 and the matrix b is an $M \times 1$ column matrix. In addition to that, the entries of matrix A are assumed to be independent and identically distributed(iid) real Gaussian variables. Given A with the above prop-

erties, the matrix $W = A^T A$ is a Wishart matrix with corresponding Wishart density $(P_{N,M}(W))$ with respect to corresponding Lebesgue measure dW .

$$P_{N,M}(W) = C_{N,M} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \text{Tr} W} (\det W)^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} \quad (1.2)$$

The entries of b are also assumed to be iid Gaussian random variables with mean 0 and variance σ^2 ($b \sim N(0, \sigma^2 I_M)$). The spherical constraint on x can be imposed with unit, N as in [23], or any fixed radius up to a trivial re-scaling [49]. This thesis aims to understand the optimization landscape through the statistics of the minimal cost and the associated Lagrange multiplier, both analytically and numerically.

Methodologies and results

2.1 Optimization on Riemannian manifold

The optimization problem under consideration is of the least square cost type with spherical constraint as described in 1. The traditional optimization algorithms may be deployed assuming a flat Euclidean space whereas the current problem involves a curved space, specifically an N -sphere. In this case, taking the intrinsic geometry into account for searching for the solution proves to be efficient in an optimization setting. A specialized approach to optimization on curved spaces is Riemannian manifold optimization. A manifold (\mathcal{M}) refers to a curved space that is smooth and differentiable [32] which locally resembles R^N . In the present scenario, it is an N -sphere $\{x \in R^N, x^2 = N\}$. The gradient-based algorithm [38][41] is a popular choice for optimization by following the steepest descent, however with the necessary modifications [7] appropriate for Riemannian manifold optimization.

It is essential to review the fundamental concepts of Riemannian geometry to make the necessary modifications to Euclidean gradient descent. On Riemannian manifolds, distances, and angles deviate from those in Euclidean spaces. A metric that accurately measures distances and angles intrinsic to the manifold's geometry is necessary giving rise to the Riemannian metric tensor \mathbf{g} . For a manifold \mathcal{M} with tangent space $\mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M}$ at $x \in \mathcal{M}$, the geometrical object \mathbf{g} defines the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_x : \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M} \rightarrow R$. It facilitates measurements of lengths and angles without relying on an external reference space [35]. The metric tensor makes the Riemannian gradient measurement coordinate invariant. The Riemannian gradient at a point x is obtained by using the metric tensor to project the ambient Euclidean gradient onto the tangent space of the manifold. Finally, the Riemannian gradient is projected onto \mathcal{M} using an exponential map $exp_x : \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$, [7], to get the updated x_{t+1} .

For a spherical manifold, the Riemannian metric is $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle_x := \alpha^T \beta$ and the Euclidean gradient $\Delta H(x)$ is projected onto tangent space using linear mapping $(I - xx^T) : R^N \rightarrow \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M}$, [2][17] to get Riemannian gradient $(R.\text{grad}(H(x)))$. The negative Riemannian gradient is then projected onto the \mathcal{M} using the exponential map provided by geodesic, $\text{exp}_x := \left(x \cos \|z\| + \frac{z}{\|z\|} \sin \|z\| \right)$, where $z = -\eta R.\text{grad}(H(x)) \in \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{M}$, [45][7]. Alternatively, one can use retraction on to sphere, $R_x(z) = \frac{x+z}{\|x+z\|}$, instead of the above exponential map for computational efficiency. The Riemannian Gradient descent algorithm is shown below:

for iteration 0, Initialize $x = x_0 \in \mathcal{M} = N - \text{Sphere}$, and, step size η

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Calculate Euclidean gradient } \Delta H(x) \\
 & \text{Calculate } z = R.\text{grad}(H(x)) = (I - xx^T)\Delta H(x) \\
 & x_{new} = \text{exp}_x(-\eta z) = \left(x \cos \|z\| + \frac{z}{\|z\|} \sin \|z\| \right), \text{ or} \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad x_{new} = R_x(z) = \frac{x+z}{\|x+z\|} \\
 & \text{iterate until convergence} (\Delta H(x) < \epsilon)
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

Further, the Conjugate gradient descent algorithm [38] can be used for faster convergence in optimization problems involving strong curvature [18][45]. The Riemannian conjugate gradient descent [44][16] is the same as gradient descent in its line search on the geodesic curve except that the old gradient is also considered in deciding the current search direction in the conjugate gradient descent case [44]. The old gradient vector is parallel-transported to the origin of the new gradient, and, the combination of the parallel-transported old gradient and the new gradient gives the current search direction [44]. A new parameter β , used for combining old and new gradients, can be computed using [18] or [39].

Pymanopt [48], a toolbox similar to that of Manopt [9] in Matlab, is used for the implementation of the Riemannian manifold optimization with conjugate gradient descent for the simulation of random least square cost minimization with spherical constraint. At every instance, the random matrices A and b are generated, and x is initialized as a random point on the sphere adhering to all the assumptions detailed in 1. The conjugate gradient descent optimization is performed using [48] to solve for minimizer x, and, the minimizer x along with the minimal cost and Lagrange multiplier are stored for further analysis.

```

1 def RCGD_sphere(mu, sigma, M, N):
2     # Generate random matrix A from a Gaussian distribution
3     for i in range(1000):
4         A = np.matrix(mu+1*np.random.standard_normal(size=(M,N))).
5         reshape((M,N))
6         W=A@A.T
7         is_positive_definite = np.all(np.isreal(np.linalg.eigvals(W)
8         ))and np.all(np.linalg.eigvals(W) > 0)
9         if is_positive_definite:
10            """print ('found W')"""
11            break

```

```

10 # Generate random matrices b from a Gaussian distribution
11 e = np.random.standard_normal(size=M)
12 b=np.matrix(mu+sigma*e).reshape((M,1))
13 e = np.matrix(e).reshape((M,1))
14
15 # Define the least squares cost function and its gradient
16 # Number of dimensions
17 n = N
18 # Define the sphere manifold
19 sphere = Sphere(n,1)
20 manifold=sphere
21 @pymanopt.function.numpy(manifold)
22 def cost(X):
23     residual = np.matmul(A , X) - b
24     return np.linalg.norm(residual)**2
25 @pymanopt.function.numpy(manifold)
26 def cost_gradient(X):
27     residual = np.matmul(A , X) - b
28     return 2*np.matmul( A.T , residual)
29
30 # Create a problem with the sphere manifold and the least
31 # squares cost function
32 problem = Problem(manifold=sphere, cost=cost,
33 euclidean_gradient=cost_gradient)
34 # Create a solver
35 solver = ConjugateGradient(verbosity=0)#
36 # Solve the optimization problem
37 Xopt = solver.run(problem)
38
39 # solution
40 X_solution=Xopt.point
41 lambda_min=np.average(-(A.T @ b - (A.T @ A) @ X_solution)/
42 X_solution)
43 e_min=cost(X_solution)/2
44
45 #Flag for negative Lagrange multiplier
46 if lambda_min<0:
47     n_lg_counter=1
48 else:
49     n_lg_counter=0
50 return [n_lg_counter ,lambda_min ,e_min]

```

Listing 2.1: Pymanopt:Riemannian conjugate gradient descent on sphere

Finally, the simulation is performed a sufficiently large number of times, using the code below, for comparison of solutions with analytically derived results.

```

1 #no. of simulation runs
2 nsim=30000
3 # One or more values of standard deviation
4 sigma_vector=np.concatenate((np.linspace(0.1, 1.25, num=3),np.
5 linspace(1.26, 3, num=2)))
6 #Dimensions M and N
7 N=50
8 M=75
9 alpha=M/N
10 #probability of negative minimum Lagrange multiplier
11 neg_lagrange_flag_samples_avg=[]
12 #vectors of flag indicating the presence of negative lagrange
13 # multiplier at each simulation run for all  $\sigma$ 
14 neg_lagrange_flag_samples=[]
15 #minimal loss/cost for all simulations runs for all  $\sigma$ 
16 e_min_samples_global=[]

```

```

15 #minimum Lagrange multiplier for all simulations runs for all $\
    sigma$
16 lambda_min_samples_global=[]
17 for j in range(len(sigma_vector)):
18     #
19     e_min_samples_local=[]
20     lambda_min_samples_local=[]
21     ###
22
23     neg_lagrange_flag=[]
24     #position in sigma vector for progress update
25     print("-- "+str(j)+" --")
26     for i in range(nsim):
27         #position in nsim for progress update
28         if (i%10)==0:
29             print("....."+str(i)+"....." )
30
31         try:
32             results=RCGD_sphere(0,sigma_vector[j],M,N)
33             ###
34             lambda_min_samples_local.append(results[1])
35             e_min_samples_local.append(results[2])
36             neg_lagrange_flag.append(results[0])
37
38         except:
39             pass
40     #save all results
41     neg_lagrange_flag=np.array(neg_lagrange_flag)
42     neg_lagrange_flag_samples.append(neg_lagrange_flag)
43     neg_lagrange_flag_samples_avg.append(np.average(
        neg_lagrange_flag_samples))
44     lambda_min_samples_local=np.array(lambda_min_samples_local)
45     lambda_min_samples_global.append(lambda_min_samples_local)
46     e_min_samples_local=np.array(e_min_samples_local)
47     e_min_samples_global.append(e_min_samples_local)

```

Listing 2.2: Simulation:RCGD on sphere for given values of M,N,μ and σ

The following sections provide the viewpoint of the Lagrange multiplier method and statistical mechanics approach, as discussed in [23], in tackling the random optimization problem at hand analytically to predict the expected minimal cost and recover the large deviation function. The associated computational results are also presented in the next sections in comparison with the analytically derived results.

2.2 Lagrange multiplier Approach

2.2.1 Overview

The Lagrange multiplier approach to the optimization of the cost function 1.1 largely follows the method outlined in [10] with necessary modifications to the specific random optimization problem. To begin, a Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}_\lambda(x)$ is defined for the least square cost function with the given spherical constraint. The

associated stationarity conditions $\Delta_x \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) = 0$ combined with the constraint equation gives rise to a secular function in λ . This function in λ can be used to understand the topological properties of the optimization landscape such as topology trivialization. The number and the position of the stationary points of the cost function, provide deep insight into the random optimization landscape topology and geometry [24] as they are associated with the minimum, saddle points, and, maximum of the cost function.

The counting of stationary points of the cost function is akin to counting roots of λ of the Lagrangian as every real root of λ is a Lagrange multiplier associated with a stationary point of the cost function. For counting stationary points a Kac-Rice approach is followed as detailed in [3]. The Kac-Rice formula for the number of stationary points of Lagrangian is given as [23],

$$\mathcal{N} = \int_D \delta(f_1) \dots \delta(f_N) \left| \det \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial x_j} \right) \right| dx_1 \dots dx_N \quad (2.2)$$

for domain $D \in \mathbb{R}^N$, f_k are $\Delta_{x_k} \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x)}{\partial x_k}$, Dirac delta representation $\delta(f_k)$ are the stationarity conditions $\Delta_x \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) = 0$, and, $\det \left(\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial x_j} \right)$ is the Jacobian.

The mean number of stationary points can be derived by taking expectations on both sides.

$$\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle = \int_D \left\langle \prod_{k=1}^N \delta \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x)}{\partial x_k} \right) \cdot \left| \det \left(\partial_{k_1, k_2}^2 \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) \right) \right| \right\rangle dx_1 \dots dx_N \quad (2.3)$$

where $\langle \rho(x) \rangle = \left\langle \prod_{k=1}^N \delta \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x)}{\partial x_k} \right) \cdot \left| \det \left(\partial_{k_1, k_2}^2 \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) \right) \right| \right\rangle$ is the mean density of stationary points.

The derived analytical expressions are analyzed in the asymptotic limits. The probability density of the minimum Lagrange multiplier $P(\lambda_{min})$, with the large deviation form shown below, found in counting the mean number of stationary points using the Kac-Rice approach is used to recover the large deviation rate $\phi(\lambda)$.

$$P(\lambda_{min}) \propto e^{-\frac{N}{2} \phi(\lambda)}$$

In the asymptotic limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$ the λ^* that minimizes $\phi(\lambda)$ is the most probable minimal Lagrange multiplier. Since the minimum Lagrange multiplier λ_{min} is associated with minimal cost, a property proved in [10], λ^* is used to derive the normalized asymptotic mean minimal cost,

$$e_{min} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\varepsilon_{\lambda^*}}{N}$$

2.2.2 Lagrangian and secular function

For the cost function $H(x)$ in 1.1, the Lagrangian can be written as follows,

$$\mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) = H(x) - \frac{\lambda}{2} (x^T x - N) \quad (2.4)$$

Using the explicit expression of $H(x)$ and partially differentiating Lagrangian with respect to x and λ as below,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{L}_\lambda(x) &= H(x) - \frac{\lambda}{2}(x^T x - N) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(x^T A^T A x - 2x^T A^T b + b^T b) - \frac{\lambda}{2}(x^T x - N)\end{aligned}$$

For stationarity conditions,

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x)}{\partial x} &= (A^T A x - A^T b - \lambda x) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_\lambda(x)}{\partial \lambda} &= -\frac{1}{2}(x^T x - N) = 0\end{aligned}$$

From stationarity conditions we arrive at the following solution of x ,

$$\begin{aligned}x &= (A^T A - \lambda I_N)^{-1} A^T b \\ x &= (W - \lambda I_N)^{-1} A^T b \quad , \text{ while satisfying } x^T x = N\end{aligned}\tag{2.5}$$

where $W = A^T A$ is an $N \times N$ Wishart matrix. Using the expression of x derived above in the constraint,

$$\begin{aligned}\implies x^T x &= b^T A (W - \lambda I_N)^{-1} \times (W - \lambda I_N)^{-1} A^T b = N, \\ \implies N &= b^T A (W - \lambda I_N)^{-2} A^T b\end{aligned}\tag{2.6}$$

To further understand the topology and geometry of the optimization landscape it is convenient to express the above equation in terms of variance parameter σ representing noise. It is worthwhile to observe the following facts[23][49],

- 1) $W^{(a)} = AA^T$ is an $M \times M$ matrix associated with Wishart matrix W sharing same non-zero eigenvalues $\{s_i\}_{i=1}^N$ except that $W^{(a)}$ has $M - N$ more eigenvalues that are zero, given that $M > N$
- 2) $\frac{1}{(W - \lambda I_N)^2} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(k+1)W^k}{\lambda^{k+2}}$
- 3) $AW^k A^T = (W^{(a)})^{k+1}$, by regrouping matrices in product, for $k \geq 0$.
- 4) $W^{(a)} = \sum_{i=1}^N s_i |v_i\rangle\langle v_i|$ is the spectral decomposition of $W^{(a)}$ where $\{v_i\}$ are the normalized eigenvectors corresponding to it's singular values $\{s_i\}$

Using these observations the equation in 2.6 can be written as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned}N &= b^T A (W - \lambda I_N)^{-2} A^T b = b^T \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(k+1)AW^k A^T}{\lambda^{k+2}} b \\ &= b^T \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(k+1)(W^{(a)})^{k+1}}{\lambda^{k+2}} b = b^T \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(k+1) \sum_{i=1}^N s_i^{k+1} |v_i\rangle\langle v_i|}{\lambda^{k+2}} b \\ &= b^T \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(k+1)s_i^{k+1}}{\lambda^{k+2}} |v_i\rangle\langle v_i| b\end{aligned}$$

Identifying the sum to infinity as Arithmetic-Geometric progression with a prefactor of $\frac{s_i}{\lambda^2}$ in the above equation, the sum can be evaluated using

$$s_\infty = \frac{a}{1-r} + \frac{dr}{(1-r)^2}$$

where $a = 1, r = \frac{s_i}{\lambda}$, and $d = 1$. Substituting this sum to infinity in the previous equation, we have,

$$N = b^T \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{(\lambda - s_i)^2} |v_i\rangle\langle v_i| b$$

Recalling that $b = \xi\sigma$,

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \sigma \xi^T \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{(\lambda - s_i)^2} |v_i\rangle\langle v_i| \xi \sigma = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{(\lambda - s_i)^2} \xi^T |v_i\rangle\langle v_i| \xi \sigma^2 \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{(\lambda - s_i)^2} (\xi^T |v_i\rangle)^2 \sigma^2 \end{aligned}$$

The resultant secular function in λ is given below,

$$\boxed{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{(\lambda - s_i)^2} (\xi^T v_i)^2 = \frac{N}{\sigma^2}} \quad (2.7)$$

While every real root of λ of the Lagrangian or the secular function is a Lagrange multiplier with an associated cost $H(x_\lambda)$, the minimum of the real roots λ_{min} is associated with the minimal cost as proved in [10].

Figure 2.1: λ vs cost

$$\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 < \dots < \lambda_N \implies H(x_{\lambda_1}) < H(x_{\lambda_2}) \dots H(x_{\lambda_N})$$

This property is validated numerically by using Riemannian conjugate gradient descent 2.1 implementation of the constrained optimization of the least square cost as shown in Figure.2.1.

A numerical inspection of the secular function 2.7 gives further insight into the topology and geometry of the optimization landscape. Observing the behaviour of this function for finite N and σ for $M/N > 1$ in Figure.2.2, it is obvious that there can be 0 or 2 solutions of λ between consecutive eigenvalues of W and 1 solution with probability zero. Further, there are two more solutions, minimum solution $\lambda_{min} \in (-\infty, s_1]$ and the maximum solution $\lambda_{max} \in [s_N, \infty)$. On the

Figure 2.2: Secular Function

other hand, the values of parameters N and σ affect the number and the position of the solutions of λ . In the case of vanishing noise ($\sigma \rightarrow 0$) the number of solutions between consecutive eigenvalues tends to zero and every solution of the Lagrange multiplier corresponds to an eigenvalue resulting in $2N$ stationary points considering both $x = \pm e_k$ [23].

In contrast for $\sigma \rightarrow \infty$ for finite N , the right hand side of the equation becomes lower than the minima of left hand side in $[s_1, s_N]$ resulting in only the 2 (minima and maximum) solutions. This is called gradual topology trivialization [23] and it can be observed in the Figure.2.3.

For a finite σ and in the limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$, the number of solutions tends

Figure 2.3: Gradual topology trivialization

to 2. This is called landscape topology trivialization [23] and it can be observed in Figure.2.4 for $N \gg 1$ at a finite $\sigma > 0$. In the subsequent sections, the mean number of stationary points or roots of λ is analytically derived followed by the details of recovery of the large deviation rate of minimal λ , and thereby the associated mean minimal cost.

Figure 2.4: Landscape topology trivialization

2.2.3 Counting real Lagrange multipliers

Using Kac-Rice approach[3], the number of stationary points of the Lagrangian 2.2 can be expressed in the following way,

$$\mathcal{N} = \int d\lambda \int \delta [A^T A \mathbf{x} - A^T \mathbf{b} - \lambda \mathbf{x}] \delta (\mathbf{x}^2 - N) \left| \det \begin{pmatrix} A^T A - \lambda I_N & -\mathbf{x} \\ 2\mathbf{x}^T & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right| d\mathbf{x}$$

The averaging of the number of stationary points of Lagrangian, with respect to random A and b, is achieved by taking expectations on both sides of the equation.

$$\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle = \left\langle \int d\lambda \int \delta [A^T A \mathbf{x} - A^T \mathbf{b} - \lambda \mathbf{x}] \delta (\mathbf{x}^2 - N) \left| \det \begin{pmatrix} A^T A - \lambda I_N & -\mathbf{x} \\ 2\mathbf{x}^T & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right| d\mathbf{x} \right\rangle_{A, \mathbf{b}} \quad (2.8)$$

Averaging over b after using Fourier integral form of dirac delta function, where $\mathbf{u} = (W - \lambda I_N) \mathbf{x} = (A^T A - \lambda I_N) \mathbf{x}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \left\langle \int \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{M}{2}}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{\mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{b}}{2\sigma^2} \right\} \delta (\mathbf{u} - A^T \mathbf{b}) \right\rangle &= \left\langle \int \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{M}{2}}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{\mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{b}}{2\sigma^2} \right\} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left. \int \frac{dk}{(2\pi)^N} \exp \{ ik^T \mathbf{u} - ik^T A^T \mathbf{b} \} \right\rangle \\ &= \left\langle \int \frac{dk}{(2\pi)^N} \exp \{ ik^T \mathbf{u} \} \int \frac{d\mathbf{b}}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{M}{2}}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{\mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{b}}{2\sigma^2} - ik^T A^T \mathbf{b} \right\} \right\rangle \end{aligned}$$

Using Gaussian integral identity,

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left\langle \int \frac{dk}{(2\pi)^N} \exp\{ik^T u\} \exp\left\{-\frac{k^T A^T A k}{\sigma^2}\right\} \right\rangle \\
&= \left\langle \frac{1}{(2\pi)^N} \left(\frac{2\pi}{\sigma^2}\right)^{\frac{N}{2}} \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-u^T W^{-1} u}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \right\rangle \\
&= \left\langle \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-u^T W^{-1} u}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}} \det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \right\rangle \\
&= \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-u^T W^{-1} u}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}} \det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \\
\implies &\left\langle \int \frac{db}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{M}{2}}} \exp\left\{-\frac{\mathbf{b}^T \mathbf{b}}{2\sigma^2}\right\} \delta(\mathbf{u} - A^T \mathbf{b}) \right\rangle = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{-u^T W^{-1} u}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}} \det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \quad (2.9)
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting 2.9 in 2.8 and averaging over W using joint probability density $\mathcal{P}_N(W)$ of Wishart ensemble of $N \times N$ random matrices W ,

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{1}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}}} \int \frac{dW \mathcal{P}_N(W)}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \int d\lambda \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} d\mathbf{x} \delta(\mathbf{x}^2 - N) \\
&\quad \times \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \mathbf{x}^T [(W - \lambda I_N) W^{-1} (W - \lambda I_N)] \mathbf{x}\right\} \left| \det \begin{pmatrix} W - \lambda I_N & -\mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{2x}^T & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right|.
\end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

Integrating over \mathbf{x} , using orthogonal invariance of Wishart density which implies rotational invariance of integrands with respect to orthogonal transformations of $x \rightarrow O x \implies x = \sqrt{N} e_1$, where $e_1 = e = (1, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$. Using the following facts,

$$1) \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} d\mathbf{x} \delta(\mathbf{x}^2 - N) f(\mathbf{x}^2) = \frac{\pi^{N/2}}{\Gamma(\frac{N}{2})} N^{\frac{N-2}{2}} f(N), \quad [40]$$

$$2) x = \sqrt{N} e$$

The determinant in the integral can be written as follows,

$$\implies \left| \det \begin{pmatrix} W - \lambda I_N & -\mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{2x}^T & 0 \end{pmatrix} \right| = 2N \left| \det(\widetilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1}) \right| \quad (2.11)$$

Here, $W = \begin{pmatrix} w & \mathbf{v}^T \\ \mathbf{v} & \widetilde{W} \end{pmatrix}$, where \widetilde{W} is $N-1 \times N-1$ Wishart matrix

And the equation 2.10 can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{2N\pi^{\frac{N}{2}} N^{\frac{N-2}{2}}}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{N}{2})} \int \frac{dW \mathcal{P}_N(W)}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \int d\lambda \\
&\quad \times \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \mathbf{x}^T [(W - \lambda I_N) W^{-1} (W - \lambda I_N)] \mathbf{x}\right\} \left| \det(\widetilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1}) \right|
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{\mathcal{K}_N N}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{N}{2}\right)} \int \frac{dW \mathcal{P}_N(W)}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \int d\lambda \\ &\quad \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \mathbf{x}^T [(W - \lambda I_N) W^{-1} (W - \lambda I_N)] \mathbf{x} \right\} \left| \det \left(\widetilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1} \right) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

$$, \quad \mathcal{K}_N = \frac{2\pi^{N/2}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{N}{2}\right)} N^{\frac{N-2}{2}}$$

Given that $x = \sqrt{N}e$, the exponential term can be written as,

$$\exp \left\{ \frac{-1}{2\sigma^2} \mathbf{x}^T [(W - \lambda I_N) W^{-1} (W - \lambda I_N)] \mathbf{x} \right\} = \exp \left\{ \frac{-N}{2\sigma^2} ((W - \lambda I_N)^2 W^{-1})_{11} \right\} \quad (2.13)$$

Using 2.13 in 2.12,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{\mathcal{K}_N N}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{N}{2}\right)} \int \frac{dW \mathcal{P}_N(W)}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} W} \int d\lambda \\ &\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{-N}{2\sigma^2} ((W - \lambda I_N)^2 W^{-1})_{11} \right\} \left| \det \left(\widetilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1} \right) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

Observe that,

- 1) Assuming $W^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} p & \mathbf{y}^T \\ \mathbf{y} & B \end{pmatrix}$, solving the system of linear equations listed below results in [49],

$$W W^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} w & \mathbf{v}^T \\ \mathbf{v} & \widetilde{W} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p & \mathbf{y}^T \\ \mathbf{y} & B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & I_{N-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

- i) $\implies [W^{-1}]_{11} = p = \frac{1}{w - \mathbf{v}^T \widetilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v}}$
- ii) $(W - \lambda I_N)^2 W^{-1} = [W^2 - 2\lambda W + \lambda^2 I_N] W^{-1} = W - 2\lambda I_N + \lambda^2 W^{-1}$
- iii) $\left[(W - \lambda I_N)^2 W^{-1} \right]_{11} = [W - 2\lambda I_N + \lambda^2 W^{-1}]_{11} = W - 2\lambda + \frac{\lambda^2}{w - \mathbf{v}^T \widetilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v}}$

- 2) JPD of Wishart ensemble is given as,

$$\mathcal{P}_N(W) = C_{N,M} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \text{Tr} W} (\det W)^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}}$$

- 3) Schur complement [12] implies that w, \widetilde{W} and $w - \mathbf{v}^T \widetilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v}$ are positive definite and, the positive definiteness concerning each of the above elements is represented by Heaviside step function θ . The change of measure and the determinant in the integral can be re-written as below,

$$\begin{aligned} dW &= \theta(w) \theta \left(w - \mathbf{v}^T \widetilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right) dw d\mathbf{v} d\widetilde{W} \\ \det W &= \det \widetilde{W} \det \left(w - \mathbf{v}^T \widetilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right) = \left(w - \mathbf{v}^T \widetilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right) \det \widetilde{W} \end{aligned}$$

Using the above facts and substituting in corresponding positions in 2.14, we arrive at,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{\mathcal{K}_N N C_{N,M}}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}}} \int d\lambda \iiint e^{-\frac{N}{2} \text{Tr} \tilde{W}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} w} \left[w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right]^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} [\det \tilde{W}]^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} \\ &\quad \times \theta(w) \theta \left(w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right) dw d\mathbf{v} d\tilde{W} \\ &\quad \times \exp \left\{ -\frac{N}{2\sigma^2} \left(w - 2\lambda + \frac{\lambda^2}{w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v}} \right) \right\} \left| \det \left(\tilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1} \right) \right| \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging and separating w and \mathbf{v} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{\mathcal{K}_N N C_{N,M}}{(2\pi\sigma^2)^{\frac{N}{2}}} \int d\lambda \int d\tilde{W} [\det \tilde{W}]^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \text{Tr} \tilde{W}} e^{\frac{N\lambda}{\sigma^2}} \left| \det \left(\tilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1} \right) \right| \\ &\quad \times \int \int \theta(w) \theta \left(w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right) dw d\mathbf{v} \left[w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right]^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} \\ &\quad \times e^{-\frac{N}{2} w \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) - \frac{N\lambda^2}{2\sigma^2} \left[w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right]^{-1}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

Here the integral corresponding to w and \mathbf{v} is \mathcal{I} as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} &= \int_{R^{N-1}} d\mathbf{v} \int_0^\infty dw \theta(w) \theta \left(w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right) \left[w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right]^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} \\ &\quad \times e^{-\frac{N}{2} w \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) - \frac{N\lambda^2}{2\sigma^2} \left[w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v} \right]^{-1}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

By change of variables, $w \rightarrow q = w - \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v}$, $\theta(x) = 1$ for $x > 0$, and, applying Gaussian integral identity for explicit evaluation of integral in \mathbf{v} , we can further rewrite \mathcal{I} as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} &= \int_{R^{N-1}} d\mathbf{v} \int_0^\infty dq \theta(q) q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) q} e^{-\frac{N\lambda^2}{2\sigma^2} \frac{1}{q}} \\ \mathcal{I} &= \int_{R^{N-1}} d\mathbf{v} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) \mathbf{v}^T \tilde{W}^{-1} \mathbf{v}} \int_0^\infty dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) q} e^{-\frac{N\lambda^2}{2\sigma^2} \frac{1}{q}} \\ \mathcal{I} &= \frac{(2\pi)^{\frac{N-1}{2}}}{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[N \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) \tilde{W}^{-1} \right]} \int_0^\infty dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) q} e^{-\frac{N\lambda^2}{2\sigma^2} \frac{1}{q}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

Now that we have integrated out \mathbf{v} ,

i) re-scaling $q \rightarrow \frac{|\lambda|}{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}} q$ and,

ii) using $\det^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[N \left(1 + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) \tilde{W}^{-1} \right] = \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{N(1+\sigma^2)} \right)^{\frac{N-1}{2}} \det^{\frac{1}{2}} \tilde{W}$

The \mathcal{I} in 2.17 can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I} &= (2\pi)^{\frac{N-1}{2}} \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{N(1+\sigma^2)} \right)^{\frac{N-1}{2}} \det^{\frac{1}{2}} \widetilde{W} \left(\frac{|\lambda|}{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}} \right)^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} \left(\frac{|\lambda|}{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}} \right)^1 \\ &\quad \times \int_0^\infty dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2}(1+\frac{1}{\sigma^2})} \left(\frac{|\lambda|}{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}} q \right)^{\frac{-N\lambda^2}{2\sigma^2}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}^q} \\ \implies \mathcal{I} &= \left(\frac{2\pi\sigma^2}{N} \right)^{\frac{N-1}{2}} \frac{\det^{\frac{1}{2}} \widetilde{W}}{(1+\sigma^2)^{\frac{M+N-2}{4}}} |\lambda|^{\frac{M-N}{2}} \int_0^\infty dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N|\lambda|}{2\sigma^2} \sqrt{1+\sigma^2} (q+\frac{1}{q})}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

Substituting 2.18 in 2.15, The following result for the mean number of Lagrange multipliers is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle &= \frac{N\mathcal{K}_N C_{N,M}}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \frac{1}{N^{\frac{N-1}{2}}} \frac{1}{(1+\sigma^2)^{\frac{M+N-2}{4}}} \int_{-\infty}^\infty d\lambda e^{\frac{N\lambda}{\sigma^2}} |\lambda|^{\frac{M-N}{2}} \\ &\quad \times \int_0^\infty dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2\sigma^2} |\lambda| \sqrt{1+\sigma^2} (q+\frac{1}{q})} \\ &\quad \times \int_{(N-1) \times (N-1)} d\widetilde{W} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \text{Tr} \widetilde{W}} (\det \widetilde{W})^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} \left| \det \left(\widetilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1} \right) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

$$\text{Here, } \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda) = \int_{(N-1) \times (N-1) > 0} d\widetilde{W} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \text{Tr} \widetilde{W}} (\det \widetilde{W})^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} \left| \det \left(\widetilde{W} - \lambda I_{N-1} \right) \right| \quad (2.20)$$

From here on the integral $\Phi_{N,M}(\lambda)$ is analyzed for $\lambda > 0$ and $\lambda < 0$ separately for counting the mean number of stationary points for positive Lagrange multipliers and Negative Lagrange multipliers respectively.

For $\lambda > 0$:

Noting that,

- 1) The Eigenvalue decomposition of a Wishart matrix $W_{N \times N}$ is $O\Lambda O^{-1}$ where O is an orthogonal matrix with eigenvectors such that $O^T O = I_N$ and Λ is a diagonal matrix with eigenvalues.

- 2)

$$\int_{N \times N} \mathcal{P}(W) dW = A_N \int \mathcal{P}(\Lambda) |\Delta(\Lambda)| d\Lambda$$

where $P(W) = P_{N,M}(W)$ is the joint probability density of the entries of Wishart matrix and $\mathcal{P}(\Lambda)$ is the probability density of the eigenvalues of the Wishart matrix. Here,[49],

$$\begin{aligned} A_N &= \frac{\pi^{\frac{N(N+1)}{4}}}{N! \prod_{k=1}^N \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{2}\right)}, \text{ and,} \\ |\Delta(\Lambda)| &= \prod_{i < j} |\Lambda_{ii} - \Lambda_{jj}| \quad [33] \end{aligned}$$

- 3) Given $W = O\Lambda O^{-1}$ such that $O^T O = I_N$ for $\lambda > 0$, using diagonalization as change of variables [33],

$$dW \propto dO |\Delta(s_1, \dots, s_N)| \prod_i ds_i$$

where dO is associated Harr measure and s_i are diagonal elements of Λ .

the integral in 2.20 can be written as below using spectral decomposition,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0) &= A_{N-1} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^{N-1}} ds_1 \dots ds_{N-1} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{N-1} s_k} \\ &\times \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} s_k^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} |\Delta_{N-1}(s_1, \dots, s_{N-1})| \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} |\lambda - s_k|. \end{aligned}$$

Applying the identity [49] pertaining Dirac delta function $f(\lambda) = \int ds_N \delta(\lambda - s_N) f(s_N)$,

- 1) For a function $f(s_N) = s_N^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} s_N} \implies f(\lambda) = \lambda^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} \lambda}$ and using $f(\lambda)^{-1}$ as a pre-factor in the integral $\Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0)$ while preserving the equation.
- 2) For a function $f(s_N) = |\Delta_N(s_1, \dots, s_N)| = \left| \prod_{i < j} (s_i - s_j) \right| \implies f(\lambda) = |\Delta_N(s_1, \dots, s_{N-1})| \prod_{i < j} |s_i - s_j|$ and substituting it in $\Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0)$

We arrive at,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0) &= A_{N-1} \frac{e^{\frac{N}{2} \lambda}}{\lambda^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}}} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^N} ds_1 \dots ds_N e^{-\frac{N}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N s_k} \prod_{k=1}^N s_k^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} \\ &\times |\Delta_N(s_1, \dots, s_N)| \delta(\lambda - s_N) \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

Exploiting the similarity of $\Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0)$ and the probability density of Wishart eigenvalues given below,

$$\mathcal{P}(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N) = \frac{1}{\tilde{C}_{N,M}} e^{-\sum_{l=1}^N \frac{\lambda_l}{2}} \prod_{l=1}^N \lambda_l^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} |\Delta(\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_N)|,$$

$$\tilde{C}_{N,M} = \frac{1}{2^{-MN/2} \pi^{N/2}} \prod_{k=1}^N \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{M-N-2+k}{2}\right)$$

the integral in 2.21 can be modified as,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0) &= A_{N-1} \tilde{C}_{N,M}^* \frac{e^{\frac{N}{2} \lambda}}{\lambda^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}}} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^N} ds_1 \dots ds_N \frac{e^{-\frac{N}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N s_k} \prod_{k=1}^N s_k^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}}}{\tilde{C}_{N,M}^*} \\ &\times |\Delta_N(s_1, \dots, s_N)| \delta(\lambda - s_N), \\ \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda > 0) &= A_{N-1} \tilde{C}_{N,M}^* \frac{e^{\frac{N}{2} \lambda}}{\lambda^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}}} \frac{\langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{wish}}{N}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

Here, $\langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{wish}$ is the mean Wishart eigenvalue density. Substituting 2.22 in 2.19, the mean number of stationary points for positive Lagrange multipliers can be evaluated as below,

Since,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{N\mathcal{K}_N C_{N,M}}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \frac{1}{N^{\frac{N-1}{2}}} \frac{1}{(1+\sigma^2)^{\frac{M+N-2}{4}}} A_{N-1} \tilde{C}_{N,M}^* \frac{e^{\frac{N}{2}\lambda}}{N\lambda^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}}} \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{2N}{\pi\sigma^2}} (1+\sigma^2)^{-\frac{M+N-2}{4}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_\sigma^+ &= \sqrt{\frac{2N}{\pi\sigma^2}} (1+\sigma^2)^{-\frac{M+N-2}{4}} \int_0^\infty d\lambda \sqrt{\lambda} \exp \left\{ N\lambda \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \right) \right\} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{wish} \\ &\quad \times \int_0^\infty dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} \exp \left\{ -\frac{N}{2\sigma^2} |\lambda| \sqrt{1+\sigma^2} \left(q + \frac{1}{q} \right) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

Following the change of variables $q = e^t$ and $\sqrt{1+\sigma^2} = e^\delta$, and, modifying the associated expressions in new variables and the limits of integral as shown below,

1) $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{e}^t$

$$\text{i) } \implies q + \frac{1}{q} = e^t + e^{-t} = 2\cosh(t), \text{ and,}$$

$$\text{ii) } dq = e^t$$

2) $\sqrt{1+\sigma^2} = e^\delta$

$$\text{i) } \implies \frac{1}{\sigma^2} = \frac{1}{e^{2\delta}-1} = \frac{e^{-\delta}}{2\sinh(\delta)}$$

$$\text{ii) } \implies \frac{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}}{\sigma^2} = \frac{e^\delta}{e^{2\delta}-1} = \frac{e^\delta}{2\sinh(\delta)}$$

$$\text{iii) } \implies \frac{2}{\sigma^2} + 1 = 1 + \frac{2}{e^{2\delta}-1} = \frac{e^{2\delta}+1}{e^{2\delta}-1} = \coth(\delta)$$

the integral in 2.23 can be written as,

$$\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_\delta^+ = \sqrt{\frac{N}{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\frac{M+N-1}{2}\delta}}{\sqrt{\sinh \delta}} \int_0^\infty d\lambda \sqrt{\lambda} e^{\frac{N\lambda}{2} \coth \delta} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{wish} \int_{-\infty}^\infty dt e^{\frac{M-N}{2}t - \frac{N\lambda}{2\sinh \delta} \cosh t} \quad (2.24)$$

Identifying an integral of the Bessel-Macdonald function $K_\alpha(x)$ [1] form in 2.24, the integral can be represented concisely as shown below,

$$\boxed{\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_\delta^+ = 2\sqrt{\frac{N}{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\frac{M+N-1}{2}\delta}}{\sqrt{\sinh \delta}} \int_0^\infty d\lambda \sqrt{\lambda} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{wish} e^{\frac{N\lambda}{2} \coth \delta} K_{\frac{\nu}{2}} \left(\frac{N\lambda}{2\sinh \delta} \right).} \quad (2.25)$$

Here, $\nu = M - N$

$\langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{wish}$ can be evaluated using JPD of Wishart eigenvalues, $\mathbf{P}(s_1, \dots, s_N)$, and, Vandermonde [33] determinant of Λ

For $\lambda < 0$:

The Wishart eigenvalue density $\langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{\text{wish}}$ is vanishing and is unrelated to $\Phi_{N,M}(\lambda < 0)$ [49]. Using,

- 1) JPD of Wishart eigenvalues and spectral decomposition as before
- 2) Applying change of variables $s_k \rightarrow x_k/N$
- 3) $\because \lambda < 0, \lambda = -|\lambda|$

$\Phi_{N,M}(\lambda)$ in 2.20 for $\lambda < 0$ can be modified as,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda < 0) &= \frac{A_{N-1}}{N^{N-1}} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^{N-1}} dx_1 \dots dx_{N-1} e^{-\frac{1}{2}x_k} \\ &\times \frac{1}{N^{\frac{(N-1)(M-N-1)}{2}}} \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} x_k^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} \\ &\times \frac{1}{N^{\frac{(N-1)(N-2)}{2}}} |\Delta_{N-1}(x_1, \dots, x_{N-1})| \\ &\times \frac{1}{N^{N-1}} \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} (x_k + N|\lambda|) \end{aligned}$$

Collecting all the multiplicative constants,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda < 0) &= \frac{A_{N-1}}{N^{(N-1)(2 + \frac{M-N-1}{2} + \frac{N-2}{2})}} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^{N-1}} dx_1 \dots dx_{N-1} \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} x_k^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}x_k} \\ &\times |\Delta_{N-1}(x_1, \dots, x_{N-1})| \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} (x_k + N|\lambda|) \end{aligned}$$

Identifying the similarity with JPD of Wishart eigenvalues and multiplying and dividing $\tilde{C}_{N-1, M-1}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda < 0) &= \frac{A_{N-1} \tilde{C}_{N-1, M-1}}{N^{\frac{(N-1)(M+1)}{2}}} \int_{\mathbb{R}_+^{N-1}} dx_1 \dots dx_{N-1} \\ &\times \frac{\prod_{k=1}^{N-1} x_k^{\frac{M-N-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}x_k} |\Delta_{N-1}(x_1, \dots, x_{N-1})|}{\tilde{C}_{N-1, M-1}} \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} (x_k + N|\lambda|) \end{aligned}$$

Barring the multiplicative constants, the above expression is equivalent to the expected value of $\det [N|\lambda|I_{N-1} + X^T X]$ concerning $N-1 \times N-1$ Wishart matrix $X^T X$ where X is $M-1 \times N-1$ matrix.

$$\implies \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda < 0) = \frac{A_{N-1} \tilde{C}_{N-1, M-1}}{N^{\frac{(N-1)(M+1)}{2}}} \langle \det [N|\lambda|I_{N-1} + X^T X] \rangle_{X^T X \text{ wish}} \quad (2.26)$$

To evaluate $\langle \det [N|\lambda|I_{N-1} + X^T X] \rangle$ note that,

1) Schur complement [12] property of determinant \implies

$$\det \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} = \det D \det (A - BD^{-1}C)$$

2) Using the above property the determinant that is to be averaged in 2.26 can be extracted for suitable values of A,B,C,and, D as shown below [49].

$$\begin{aligned} \det \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{N|\lambda|}I_{N-1} & X^T \\ X & \sqrt{N|\lambda|}I_{M-1} \end{pmatrix} &= (\sqrt{N|\lambda|})^{M-1} \det \left(\sqrt{N|\lambda|}I_{N-1} - \frac{X^T X}{\sqrt{N|\lambda|}} \right) \\ &= (\sqrt{N|\lambda|})^{M-N} \det (N|\lambda|I_{N-1} - X^T X) \end{aligned}$$

3) A property of the Chiral determinant relates the determinant to be averaged to Laugerre polynomials as shown below [23].

i)

$$\left\langle \det \begin{pmatrix} tI_{N-1} & \pm X^T \\ \pm X & tI_{M-1} \end{pmatrix} \right\rangle_{wish} = (-1)^{N-1} (N-1)! t^{M-N} L_{N-1}^{M-N}(t^2), \quad \forall t$$

ii) Here $L_{N-1}^{M-N}(t^2)$ is generalized Laguerre polynomial where:

$$L_{N-1}^{M-N}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \binom{M-1}{N-1-k} \frac{(-x)^k}{k!}$$

The average of determinant in 2.26 can be extracted by substituting $t = \sqrt{N|\lambda|}$ and $|\lambda| \rightarrow -|\lambda|$ in above expressions, and, using its relationship with the above-mentioned property of Chiral determinant.

$$\begin{aligned} (-1)^{N-1} \left\langle \det \left[\sqrt{N|\lambda|}I_{N-1} + X^T X \right] \right\rangle &= (-1)^{\frac{N-M}{2}} (N|\lambda|)^{\frac{N-M}{2}} (-1)^{N-1} (N-1)! \\ &\quad \times (-1)^{\frac{M-N}{2}} (N|\lambda|)^{\frac{M-N}{2}} L_{N-1}^{M-N}(-N|\lambda|). \\ \implies \left\langle \det \left[\sqrt{N|\lambda|}I_{N-1} + X^T X \right] \right\rangle &= (N-1)! L_{N-1}^{M-N}(-N|\lambda|) \\ &= (N-1)! \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \binom{M-1}{N-1-k} \frac{(N|\lambda|)^k}{k!} \end{aligned} \tag{2.27}$$

Using 2.27 in 2.26,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{N,M}(\lambda < 0) &= \frac{A_{N-1} \tilde{C}_{N-1,M-1}}{N^{\frac{(N-1)(M+1)}{2}}} (N-1)! \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \binom{M-1}{N-1-k} \frac{(N|\lambda|)^k}{k!} \\ &= T_{N,M} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \binom{M-1}{N-1-k} \frac{(N|\lambda|)^k}{k!} \end{aligned} \tag{2.28}$$

Here $T_{N,M}$ is evaluated using explicit expressions of A_{N-1} and $\tilde{C}_{N-1,M-1}$,

$$T_{N,M} = \frac{2^{\frac{(M-1)(N-1)}{2}} \pi^{\frac{(N-1)(N-2)}{4}}}{N^{\frac{(N-1)(M+1)}{2}}} (N-1)! \prod_{k=1}^{N-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{M-k}{2}\right).$$

Substituting 2.28 in 2.19 for $\lambda < 0$ results in,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-} &= \frac{N \mathcal{K}_N C_{N,M}}{N^{\frac{N-1}{2}}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} \frac{1}{(1+\sigma^2)^{\frac{M+N-2}{4}}} \\ &\times \int_{-\infty}^0 d\lambda e^{\frac{N\lambda}{\sigma^2}} |\lambda|^{\frac{M-N}{2}} \int_0^{\infty} dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2\sigma^2} |\lambda| \sqrt{1+\sigma^2} (q+\frac{1}{q})} \\ &\times T_{N,M} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \binom{M-1}{N-1-k} \frac{(N|\lambda|)^k}{k!}. \end{aligned}$$

Using explicit expressions of \mathcal{K}_N , $C_{N,M}$, and, $T_{N,M}$, an overall multiplication factor is evaluated as shown below,

$$\frac{N \mathcal{K}_N C_{N,M}}{N^{\frac{N-1}{2}}} T_{N,M} = \frac{(N-1)! N^{\frac{M-N+2}{2}}}{2^{\frac{M+N-3}{2}}} \frac{\pi^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{N}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{M}{2}\right)}.$$

Using the overall multiplication factor evaluated above in 2.28, changing $\lambda \rightarrow -\lambda$ and the associated limits of the integral in λ , and, identifying the integral of the Bessel-Macdonald function $K_{\alpha}(x)$ form with $\alpha = \frac{\nu}{2} = \frac{M-N}{2}$ and $x = \frac{N\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}\lambda}{\sigma^2}$, the mean number of stationary points of the Lagrangian for $\lambda < 0$ can be expressed analytically as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-} &= \frac{N! N^{\frac{M-N+2}{2}}}{2^{\frac{M+N-2}{2}}} \frac{1}{\Gamma\left(\frac{N}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{M}{2}\right)} \frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{1}{(1+\sigma^2)^{\frac{M+N-2}{4}}} \\ &\times \int_0^{\infty} d\lambda e^{-\frac{N\lambda}{\sigma^2}} \lambda^{\frac{M-N}{2}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \binom{M-1}{N-1-k} \frac{(N\lambda)^k}{k!} K_{\frac{\nu}{2}} \left(N \frac{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}}{\sigma^2} \lambda \right), \end{aligned}$$

whereas the mentioned Bessel-Macdonald function [1] form in the above integral is,

$$\int_0^{\infty} dq q^{\frac{M-N-2}{2}} e^{-\frac{N\lambda}{2\sigma^2} \sqrt{1+\sigma^2} (q+\frac{1}{q})} = 2K_{\frac{\nu}{2}} \left(N \frac{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}}{\sigma^2} \lambda \right)$$

Finally,

- 1) using the following identity [29]-(6.621.3) with hypergeometric function F:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\alpha x} K_{\nu}(\beta x) x^{\mu-1} dx &= \frac{\sqrt{\pi}(2\beta)^{\nu}}{(\alpha+\beta)^{\mu+\nu}} \frac{\Gamma(\mu+\nu)\Gamma(\mu-\nu)}{\Gamma\left(\mu+\frac{1}{2}\right)} \\ &\times F\left(\mu+\nu, \nu+\frac{1}{2}, \mu+\frac{1}{2}, \frac{\alpha-\beta}{\alpha+\beta}\right). \end{aligned}$$

- 2) with $\alpha = \frac{N}{\sigma^2}$, $\beta = N \frac{\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}}{\sigma^2}$, $\nu = \frac{M-N}{2}$ and $\mu = \frac{M-N}{2} + k + 1$

The mean number of stationary points of the Lagrangian for $\lambda < 0$ can be

analytically expressed as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-} &= 2\sqrt{\pi} \frac{(N-1)!(M-1)!}{\Gamma\left(\frac{N}{2}\right)\Gamma\left(\frac{M}{2}\right)} \frac{\sigma^{M-N-1}}{(1+\sqrt{1+\sigma^2})^{M-N} (2\sqrt{1+\sigma^2})^{N-1}} \\
&\times \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{1+\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}} \right)^{k+1} \frac{1}{\Gamma(N-k)\Gamma\left(\frac{M-N+1}{2}+k+1\right)} \\
&\times F\left(M-N+k+1, \frac{M-N+1}{2}, \frac{M-N+1}{2}+k+1, \frac{1-\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}}{1+\sqrt{1+\sigma^2}}\right).
\end{aligned} \tag{2.29}$$

The mean total number of stationary points of the Lagrangian is the sum of the contributions from $\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-}$ and $\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{+}$.

$$\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma} = \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-} + \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{+}$$

Both $\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-}$ and $\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{+}$ can be easily evaluated at finite N and σ using 2.29 and 2.25 respectively. The numerical simulation of $\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\sigma}^{-}$ is performed using Reimannian conjugate gradient descent 2.1 implementation of the optimization problem and the results are presented below in Figure.2.6 in comparison with the results using the analytical formula derived in 2.29. It is evident from the visualization that the analytical and numerical results agree.

Figure 2.5: Counting Negative Lagrange multipliers: sim~ simulation result,Analy~Analytical result

2.2.4 Discussion of asymptotics

To begin with, the expression in 2.24 can be written in a form amenable to asymptotic analysis as shown below,

$$\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\delta}^{+} = \sqrt{\frac{N}{\pi}} \frac{e^{-\frac{M+N-1}{2}\delta}}{\sqrt{\sinh \delta}} \int_0^{\infty} d\lambda \sqrt{\lambda} e^{\frac{N\lambda}{2} \coth \delta} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{\text{wish}} \mathcal{J}_N(\lambda) \tag{2.30}$$

where,

$$\mathcal{J}_N(\lambda) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{\frac{M-N}{2}t - \frac{N\lambda}{2\sinh\delta} \cosh t} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt e^{-\frac{N}{2}\mathcal{L}(t)}$$

The Laplace method of evaluating integral over t in the limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$ using the stationary point of $\mathcal{L}(t)$ can be used to approximate $\mathcal{J}_N(\lambda)$. Using this approximation in 2.30 gives rise to an $\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)$ with a prefactor $\frac{-N}{2}$ in the exponent of the integral in λ . The overall integral is approximated as shown here,[23][49],

$$\langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\delta}^{+} \propto 2e^{-\frac{N(\alpha-1)\delta}{2}} \int_0^{\infty} d\lambda \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 + \kappa^2}}} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{\text{wish}} e^{-\frac{N}{2}\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)} \quad (2.31)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_1(\lambda) &= (\alpha - 1) \left[\frac{\sqrt{\lambda^2 + \kappa^2}}{\kappa} - \log \left(\frac{\kappa + \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \kappa^2}}{\lambda} \right) - \lambda \frac{\sqrt{(\alpha - 1) + \kappa^2}}{(\alpha - 1)\kappa} \right], \\ \kappa &= (\alpha - 1) \sinh \delta, \\ \delta &= \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \sigma^2) \end{aligned} \quad (2.32)$$

The integral above demands the application of Laplace or saddle point method again over λ . Evaluating the second derivative of $\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)$ at the stationary point $\lambda^* = \alpha - 1$ shows that $\frac{d^2\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)}{d\lambda^2} < 0$ implying that it is a maxima. The analog of wigner semicircle distribution in Gaussian orthogonal ensemble case for Wishart ensemble is Marchenko-Pastur(MP) distribution implying $\langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{\text{wish}} = \langle \rho_N^{MP}(\lambda) \rangle$ for $\lambda \in [s_-, s_+]$ ($s_{\pm} = (\sqrt{\alpha} \pm 1)^2$).

However, given that the stationary point is a maxima, the integral in 2.31 will be dominated by region outside $[s_-, s_+]$ for finite $\kappa = o(1)$ and thus δ . This regime corresponds to 'landscape topology trivialization' referred earlier with only 2 solutions, λ_{min} and λ_{max} [23]. For the regime with the limits of $\delta \rightarrow 0, N \rightarrow \infty$, and, for a finite $\gamma = \frac{\delta N}{4}$, the exponential term can be approximated using the first order Taylor expansions in its exponent and using Marchenko-Pastur(MP) distribution $\langle \rho_N^{MP}(\lambda) \rangle$ [49]. Using such asymptotic approximation for \mathcal{N}_{δ}^{+} it is observed that the asymptotic mean number of Lagrange multipliers is of the order N . From this asymptotic regime of $\delta = \kappa = o(\frac{1}{N})$ the mean number of Lagrange multipliers decreases with increasing δ and thus γ .

For $\gamma \gg 1$ it is obvious that the \mathcal{N}_{δ}^{+} in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ is dominated by spectral edges. It is found from leading order contribution computed by scaling λ to accommodate the vicinity of the spectral edges, $\langle \mathcal{N}_{\delta}^{+} \rangle$ is of the order unity as δ increases to the order of $o(N^{-\frac{1}{3}})$. For any $\alpha > 1$, the λ_{min} is still positive in this regime as $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_{\delta \sim N^{-1/3}}^{-} = 0$, [23]. Since the lowest possible number of Lagrange multipliers is 2, this regime be identified as a new asymptotic regime where the Marchenko-Pastur(MP) distribution can not be solely relied upon. Using $\rho_{edge}(\xi)$ given in terms of Airy function $Ai(\xi)$ [23] instead of Marchenko-Pastur(MP) distribution and expanding terms in $\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)$ to higher order of $\frac{k}{\lambda}$, it can be shown that the asymptotic mean number of Lagrange multipliers is 2 for any fixed σ , [49].

2.2.5 Large deviation rate and minimal cost

Firstly, note that only the smallest Lagrange multiplier can be smaller than the minimum eigenvalue Of the Wishart matrix W . In the asymptotic limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$ the eigenvalues of the Wishart matrix are distributed in $[s_-, s_+]$. Hence, it is only consequential that all $\lambda > \lambda_{min}$ lie between the spectral edges with a high probability except the lowest Lagrange multiplier λ_{min} . Thus the asymptotic probability density of λ in $(0, s_-)$ is the same as the probability density of the minimum Lagrange multiplier. Identifying $P_+(\lambda)$ in 2.31 as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathcal{N} \rangle_\delta^+ &\propto 2e^{-\frac{N(\alpha-1)\delta}{2}} \int_0^\infty d\lambda \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 + k^2}}} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{\text{wish}} e^{-\frac{N}{2}\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)} \\ &\implies P_+(\lambda) \approx 2e^{-\frac{N(\alpha-1)\delta}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{\lambda^2 + k^2}}} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle_{\text{wish}} e^{-\frac{N}{2}\mathcal{L}_1(\lambda)} \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_1(\lambda) &= (\alpha - 1) \left[\frac{\sqrt{\lambda^2 + \kappa^2}}{\kappa} - \log \left(\frac{\kappa + \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \kappa^2}}{\lambda} \right) - \lambda \frac{\sqrt{(\alpha - 1) + \kappa^2}}{(\alpha - 1)\kappa} \right], \\ \kappa &= (\alpha - 1) \sinh \delta, \\ \delta &= \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \sigma^2) \end{aligned}$$

For $N \gg 1$, the large deviation rate corresponding to the density of λ in spectral edges outside the scope of Marchenko-Pastur density is given as [19],

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \rho_N(\lambda) \rangle &\propto e^{-\frac{N}{2}\mathcal{L}_2}, \\ \mathcal{L}_2(\lambda) &= -\sqrt{(\lambda - s_-)(\lambda - s_+)} - 2 \log(\alpha + 1 + \lambda - \sqrt{(\lambda - s_-)(\lambda - s_+)}) \\ &\quad + 2(\alpha - 1) \log(\alpha + \lambda - 1 + \sqrt{(\lambda - s_-)(\lambda - s_+)}) \end{aligned} \tag{2.33}$$

Using both 2.32 and 2.33, the probability density of minimum Lagrange multiplier in $(0, s_-)$ can be approximated in large deviation form as given below [25],

$$\begin{aligned} P(\lambda) &\propto e^{-\frac{N}{2}\phi(\lambda)} \\ \phi(\lambda) &= \mathcal{L}_1(\lambda) + \mathcal{L}_2(\lambda) + \text{Constant} \\ \text{constant} &= \frac{\alpha + 1}{2} \log(1 + \sigma^2) + 2(\alpha - 2) \log\left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{\alpha}}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{2.34}$$

In the asymptotic limit of $N \rightarrow \infty$, the $\lambda = \lambda^*$ that minimizes $\phi(\lambda)$ has the maximum probability density $P(\lambda^*)$ given that $\frac{d^2\phi(\lambda)}{d\lambda^2} < 0$. The most probable value λ^* of minimum Lagrange multiplier λ_{min} can be deduced as a stationary point by solving $\frac{d\phi(\lambda)}{d\lambda} = 0$ followed by verifying the condition $\frac{d^2\phi(\lambda)}{d\lambda^2} < 0$ for it to be maxima. Though it is straight forward it is cumbersome. An alternate way of approaching this problem is realizing that the secular function in 2.7

can be useful in solving for λ^* . Firstly writing secular function in 2.7 in a form convenient for later analysis as shown below,

$$g(\lambda) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{(\lambda - s_i)^2} (\xi^T \mathbf{v}_i)^2 = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \quad (2.35)$$

The above function is random as \mathbf{b} and Wishart matrix \mathbf{W} are random. Also, note that the minimum of the solutions of λ of $g(\lambda)$ lies outside the spectral interval of Wishart matrices and thus $g(\lambda)$ is self-averaging for such λ . So the proposition [49] that the typical value λ^* of minimum Lagrange multiplier is the solution of,

$$\langle \langle g(\lambda^*) \rangle \rangle_{\mathbf{b}} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2}$$

can be verified by checking whether a solution of above equation satisfies the condition $\frac{d\phi(\lambda^*)}{d\lambda} = 0$. Averaging over \mathbf{b} , [49],

$$\langle g(\lambda) \rangle_{\mathbf{b}} = \frac{1}{N} \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{\mathbf{W}}{(\lambda - \mathbf{W})^2} \right\} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \left[\frac{1}{N} \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{\mathbf{W}}{\lambda - \mathbf{W}} \right\} \right] = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \left[\lambda \frac{1}{N} \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda - \mathbf{W}} \right\} \right]$$

Averaging over \mathbf{W} using Wishart JPD,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \langle g(\lambda) \rangle \rangle_{\mathbf{b}} &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \left[\lambda \frac{1}{N} \left\langle \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda - \mathbf{W}} \right\} \right\rangle_{\text{wish}} \right] \\ &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \left[\lambda \left(-\frac{2}{\lambda} \frac{\sqrt{s_+ s_-} - \lambda - \sqrt{(\lambda - s_-)(\lambda - s_+)}}{(\sqrt{s_+} - \sqrt{s_-})^2} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \end{aligned}$$

Solving the above quadratic equation in λ with $s_{\pm} = (\sqrt{\alpha} \pm 1)^2$ gives,

$$\lambda = (\alpha + 1) \pm \sqrt{\alpha} \frac{\sigma^2 + 2}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + 1}} = (\alpha + 1) \pm \sqrt{\alpha} \left[\sqrt{1 + \sigma^2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \sigma^2}} \right]$$

Since,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{g}(0) &= \frac{1}{N} \left\langle (\xi^T \mathbf{v}_i)^2 \right\rangle \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{s_i} \right\rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\alpha\beta} \langle \xi_{\alpha} \xi_{\beta} \rangle \mathbf{v}_{\alpha} \mathbf{v}_{\beta} \left\langle \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{s_i} \right\rangle \\ &= \sum_{\alpha} \mathbf{v}_{\alpha}^2 \left\langle \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{s_i} \right\rangle_{\text{wish}, N \rightarrow \infty} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha - 1} = \frac{1}{\sigma^2} \end{aligned}$$

In the solutions of λ of the quadratic equation, the solution with a minus sign is λ^* as only that solution is zero for $\sigma^2 = \alpha - 1$ in line with the expectation. The condition $\frac{d\phi(\lambda^*)}{d\lambda} = 0$ also is verified at this solution.

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} \lambda^* &= (\alpha + 1) - \sqrt{\alpha} \left[\sqrt{1 + \sigma^2} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \sigma^2}} \right] \\ &= (\sqrt{\alpha} - \sqrt{1 + \sigma^2}) \left(\sqrt{\alpha} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \sigma^2}} \right) \end{aligned}} \quad (2.36)$$

Finally, consider the cost function $H(x)$ in 1.1,

$$H(x) = \frac{1}{2}(A\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{b})^T(A\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{b}) = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{x}^T W \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{b}^T A \mathbf{x} + \frac{\mathbf{b}^2}{2}$$

Using $\mathbf{x} = (W - \lambda I)^{-1} A^T \mathbf{b}$, expression of \mathbf{x} from stationarity conditions, in $H(x)$ and substituting $\mathbf{x}^T \mathbf{x} = N$ in the resultant expression,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_\lambda &= H((W - \lambda I)^{-1} A^T \mathbf{b}) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{b}^T A \frac{1}{W - \lambda I} (W - \lambda I + \lambda I) \frac{1}{W - \lambda I} A^T \mathbf{b} - \mathbf{b}^T A \frac{1}{W - \lambda I} A^T \mathbf{b} + \frac{\mathbf{b}^2}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\lambda N + \mathbf{b}^2 + \mathbf{b}^T A \frac{1}{\lambda I - W} A^T \mathbf{b} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Using the fact [49] that,

$$A \frac{1}{\lambda - W} A^T = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{s_i}{\lambda - s_i} |\mathbf{v}_i\rangle \langle \mathbf{v}_i| = \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{W}{\lambda - W} \right\}$$

the expectation of normalized minimal cost can be re-written as shown below with $\lambda = \lambda^*$,

$$\frac{\langle \mathcal{E}_{\lambda^*} \rangle}{N} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\lambda_* + \frac{\langle \mathbf{b}^2 \rangle}{N} + \sigma^2 \frac{1}{N} \left\langle \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{W}{\lambda_* - W} \right\} \right\rangle_{wish} \right]$$

Substituting known $\left\langle \text{Tr} \left\{ \frac{W}{\lambda_* - W} \right\} \right\rangle_{wish}$ and $\frac{\langle \mathbf{b}^2 \rangle}{N} = \frac{M\sigma^2}{N}$, and, λ^* the asymptotic mean minimal cost is derived as [23][49],

$$\boxed{\frac{\langle \mathcal{E}_{\lambda^*} \rangle}{N} = e_{min} := \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)} - 1 \right)^2} \quad (2.37)$$

The numerical simulation of random least square minimization for 10000 runs is achieved by using the Riemannian conjugate gradient descent algorithm 2.1. The analytical and numerical results of normalized minimal-cost solution and large deviation rate of minimum Lagrange multiplier are compared in Figure.2.6 and Figure.2.7 respectively.

Figure 2.6: λ_{min} simulation using Reimannian conjugate gradient descent

Figure 2.7: Large deviation rate: simulation(LDR sim) vs analytical(LDR)

2.3 Statistical Mechanics Approach

2.3.1 Overview

The approach of statistical mechanics of disordered systems to search for x on a sphere $x^2 = N$ that minimizes the cost function $H(x)$ involves defining a partition function $Z(\beta)$, where $\beta > 0$ is an auxiliary parameter called inverse temperature, as shown below:

$$Z = \int_{x^2=N} e^{-\beta H(x)} dx \quad (2.38)$$

For suppose, the minimal cost ε_{min} of $H(x)$ is incident at x_{min} which is not necessarily unique then the above integral can be evaluated using Laplace's method in the asymptotic limit of $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ resulting in the following leading exponential behavior and recovery of minimal cost:

$$Z \propto e^{-\beta \varepsilon_{min}} \quad (2.39)$$

$$\varepsilon_{min} = - \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\log Z}{\beta} \quad (2.40)$$

Since the minimization problem at hand involves a random version of the least square cost, it is imperative to look at aggregate statistics of minimal cost, which depend on the feasibility of dealing with the logarithmic function on the right-hand side. But even in the simplest yet non-trivial case of finding the expected minimal cost, the average of logarithm of partition functions needs to be evaluated. The theory of spin glasses [13] achieved progress in averaging the logarithm of partition functions in special cases involving normally distributed energy/cost functions[46]. But in the present case, as noted in [23], the cost function is a sum of squares of normally distributed entities. But the replica trick, a heuristic approach from theoretical physics, e.g.[37], comes in handy in finding the mean minimal cost using the replicated disorder averaged partition function in the limit of $n \rightarrow 0$, the expectation of integer moments of the partition function $\langle Z^n \rangle$ in the above limit, to circumvent the problem of directly finding $\langle \log(Z) \rangle$. The ensemble average of $\log(Z)$ and subsequently the expected value of minimal cost is recovered by applying limits of n and β as shown below:

Applying expectation on both sides in 2.40,

$$\langle \varepsilon_{min} \rangle = - \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\beta} \langle \log(Z) \rangle \quad (2.41)$$

Using replica trick,

$$\langle \log(Z) \rangle = \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{n} \log \langle Z^n \rangle \quad (2.42)$$

By substituting 2.42 in 2.41,

$$\langle \varepsilon_{min} \rangle = - \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\beta} \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{n} \log \langle Z^n \rangle \quad (2.43)$$

The other useful feature of the minimal cost of random least square type minimization is the fluctuation around the expected minimal cost. Again, the replica trick proves to be useful in characterizing fluctuations around mean minimal loss via the large deviations approach at large $N \gg 1$. This approach starts with the assumption of a large deviation form for the probability density of ε_{min} . By using this probability density and suitable modifications to the evaluation of limits of the replicated disorder averaged partition function, a relation between the exponent in replicated disorder averaged partition function evaluated by Laplace's method at large $N \gg 1$ and the large deviation function is derived via Legendre transformation. Finally, the large deviation rate is recovered using inverse Legendre transformation as shown below.

Assuming, $R(e)$ and $L(e)$ are the leading prefactor and the large deviation rate respectively, the probability density of the minimal cost is,

$$P_N(\varepsilon_{min}) \approx R(e)e^{-NL(e)}, e = \frac{\varepsilon_{min}}{N} \quad (2.44)$$

Keeping the product $n\beta := s$ fixed and using 2.41, the limits $n \rightarrow 0$ and $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ of replicated disorder averaged partition function $\langle Z^n \rangle$ can be evaluated as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \langle Z^n \rangle &= \lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle Z^n \rangle \\ &= \lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle e^{n \log(Z)} \rangle \\ &= \lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle e^{\frac{s}{\beta} \log(Z)} \rangle \\ &= \lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle e^{-Nse} \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (2.45)$$

Now, using the large deviation form of the probability density of minimal cost from 2.44, the expectation in the above expression can be further rewritten as shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle Z^n \rangle &= \lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle e^{-Nse} \rangle \\ &= \int P_N(e) e^{-Nse} de \\ &\approx \int R(e) e^{-N(L(e)+se)} de \end{aligned} \quad (2.46)$$

Applying Laplace's method for evaluating the above integral for large $N \gg 1$, results in,

$$\lim_{n = \frac{s}{\beta}, \beta \rightarrow \infty} \langle Z^n \rangle \approx g(s) e^{N\phi(s)}, \phi(s) = -\min_e (se + L(e)) \quad (2.47)$$

As noted in [23], $\phi(s)$ is related to the large deviation rate by Legendre transform. Thus, the large deviation rate can be recovered as an inverse Legendre transform assuming that $\phi(s)$ can be found.

$$L(e) = -(es^* + \phi(s^*)), e = -\phi'(s^*) \quad (2.48)$$

It is obvious from 2.43 and 2.48 that analytical evaluation of replicated disorder averaged function is necessary to progress on deriving expected minimal value and large deviation rate. The averaging of the replicated partition function followed by necessary derivations to arrive at the analytical solutions for the expectation and the large deviation function of the minimal cost are provided in the following section.

2.3.2 Averaging of the replicated partition function

For a given loss function $H(x)$ with a spherical constraint on x , 2.38 defines the partition function from a statistical mechanics point of view, and, by using the given cost function from 1.1 the partition function can be expressed as:

$$Z = \int_{x^2=N} e^{-\beta \frac{\|Ax-b\|^2}{2}} dx \quad (2.49)$$

Expressing the cost in the form of the summation of M linear equations in N unknowns, the partition function can be re-written as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Substituting } \frac{\|Ax-b\|^2}{2} &= \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{(a_k x - b_k)^2}{2} \text{ in 2.49,} \\ Z &= \int_{x^2=N} e^{-\beta \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{(a_k x - b_k)^2}{2}} dx \end{aligned} \quad (2.50)$$

Representing $(a_k x - b_k)$ as $V_k(x)$ for simplicity,

$$Z = \int_{x^2=N} e^{-\beta \sum_{k=1}^M \frac{V_k^2(x)}{2}} dx \quad (2.51)$$

Consider the Gaussian integral identity in an auxiliary variable u_k as shown below:

$$\int_R e^{-\frac{1}{2}u_k^2 - i\sqrt{\beta}V_k(x)u_k} du_k = \sqrt{2\pi} e^{-\beta \frac{V_k^2(x)}{2}} \quad (2.52)$$

It is obvious that the above identity helps in re-writing the partition function from 2.51 in the below format:

$$Z = \int_{x^2=N} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{M}{2}}} \int_R \dots \int_R e^{-\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^M u_k^2 - i\sqrt{\beta} \sum_{k=1}^M V_k(x)u_k} du_1 \dots du_M dx \quad (2.53)$$

By further simplification by representing new auxiliary variables as $U(U = (u_1, u_2, \dots, u_M))$, the partition function is,

$$Z = \int_{x^2=N} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{M}{2}}} \int_{R^M} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(U.U) - i\sqrt{\beta} \sum_{k=1}^M V_k(x)u_k} dudx \quad (2.54)$$

The Replicated disorder averaged partition function is the expectation of the product of n identical copies of Z with index a=1,2,...,n as shown below,

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle Z^n \rangle &= \int_{R^{Mn}} \prod_{a=1}^n \left(\frac{du_a}{(2\pi)^{\frac{M}{2}}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(u_a \cdot u_a)} \right) \\
&\int_{D_N} \dots \int \prod_{a=1}^n dx_a \prod_{k=1}^M \langle e^{-i\sqrt{\beta}[u_a]_k V_k(x_a)} \rangle \\
&= \int_{R^{Mn}} \prod_{a=1}^n \left(\frac{du_a}{(2\pi)^{\frac{M}{2}}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(u_a \cdot u_a)} \right) \\
&\int_{D_N} \dots \int \prod_{k=1}^M \langle e^{-i\sqrt{\beta} \sum_{a=1}^n [u_a]_k V_k(x_a)} \rangle \prod_{a=1}^n dx_a
\end{aligned} \tag{2.55}$$

Here, $D_N = \{ x_a^2 = N, \forall a \}$ is a union of spheres.

To progress further in the evaluation, it is evident that we need to be able to evaluate the following expectation:

$$\prod_{k=1}^M \langle e^{-i\sqrt{\beta} \sum_{a=1}^n [u_a]_k V_k(x_a)} \rangle$$

The fact that $v_k(x)$ is Gaussian with mean zero and covariance of the form $\delta_{kl} f(\frac{x_a x_b}{N})$, an Isotropic Gaussian distributed random field on a sphere with covariance depending only on the angle between vectors as noted in [20] and [22] is useful in the above evaluation. The choice in the present case is $\sigma^2 + u = f(u)$. Also, using the fact that the linear combination of Gaussian random variables is again a Gaussian random variable combined with the knowledge that $v_k(x)$ is a Gaussian random variable it is obvious that the following is a Gaussian random variable.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{Z} &= -i\sqrt{\beta} \sum_{a=1}^n [u_a]_k V_k(x_a) \text{ with mean 0 and variance } \langle \mathcal{Z}^2 \rangle, \\
\langle \mathcal{Z}^2 \rangle &= -\beta \sum_{a,b=1}^n [u_a]_k [u_b]_k f\left(\frac{x_a x_b}{N}\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{2.56}$$

Using the identity $\langle e^h \rangle = e^{\frac{1}{2}\langle h^2 \rangle}$ for a Gaussian random variable and 2.56, the expectation in 2.55 can be written as,

$$\prod_{k=1}^M \langle e^{-i\sqrt{\beta} \sum_{a=1}^n [u_a]_k V_k(x_a)} \rangle_v = e^{-\frac{\beta(u_a \cdot u_b) f(\frac{x_a x_b}{N})}{2}} \tag{2.57}$$

Substituting 2.57 in 2.55, results in the following proportionality of the replicated disorder averaged partition function :

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle Z^n \rangle &\propto \int_{D_N} \dots \int \prod_{a=1}^n dx_a \int_{R^{Mn}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(u_a \cdot u_a) - \frac{\beta(u_a \cdot u_b) f(\frac{x_a x_b}{N})}{2}} \prod_{a=1}^n du_a \\
&\propto \int_{D_N} \dots \int \prod_{a=1}^n dx_a \int_{R^{Mn}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}[u_1, \dots, u_n][I_n + \beta f(\frac{x_a x_b}{N})][u_1, \dots, u_n]} \prod_{a=1}^n du_a
\end{aligned} \tag{2.58}$$

where the integral over u_a is a multivariate n-dimensional Gaussian integration taken M times. Applying the following proportionality from Gaussian integral

identity for matrices to 2.58, we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \int e^{-\frac{1}{2}XAX^T} &\propto \det(A)^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \text{ for a real symmetric positive definite matrix A,} \\ < Z^n > &\propto \int_{D_N} \dots \int \prod_{a=1}^n dx_a \det[I_n + \beta f(\frac{x_a x_b}{N})]^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.59)$$

In 2.59 the integrand depends on N-Component vector x_a only via $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ scalar products $q_{ab} = x_a x_b$ which are the entries of a matrix $Q = X^T X$ where $X = [x_1, \dots, x_n]$ is an $N \times n$ matrix. Such an integral is invariant under arbitrary simultaneous rotation of all vectors x_a . The integral in 2.59 with such invariance is efficiently dealt with by using the fundamental identity derived in [21] and presented in [20] as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{|x_1| < L} \dots \int_{|x_n| < L} \mathcal{I}(X^T X) dx_1 \dots dx_n &= \mathcal{C}_{N,n} \int_{D_L^{(Q)}} \mathcal{I}(Q) [\det(Q)]^{\frac{N-n-1}{2}} dQ, \\ \text{where, } \mathcal{C}_{N,n} &\text{ is a known constant for given N and } n (N \geq n), \\ D_L^{(Q)} &= \{Q \geq 0, q_{aa} \leq L^2, a = 1, 2, \dots, n\}, \text{ and,} \\ dQ &= \prod_{a \leq b} dq_{ab} \end{aligned} \quad (2.60)$$

Applying 2.60 to the current case 2.59 yields,

$$\begin{aligned} < Z^n > &\propto \int_{D_N^{(Q)}} dQ (\det Q)^{\frac{N-n-1}{2}} \left(\det [I_n + \beta \hat{f}(Q)] \right)^{-\frac{M}{2}}, \\ \hat{f}(Q) &= f\left(\frac{x_a x_b}{N}\right) \text{ is an } n \times n \text{ matrix} \end{aligned} \quad (2.61)$$

Since we are ultimately interested in asymptotic behavior, re-writing 2.61 in compatible way for asymptotic analysis:

$$\begin{aligned} < Z^n > &\propto \int_{D_N^{(Q)}} dQ (\det Q)^{\frac{-n-1}{2}} e^{\frac{N}{2} \log(\det Q) - \frac{M}{2} \log \det [I_n + \beta \hat{f}(Q)]} \\ &\propto \int_{D_N^{(Q)}} dQ (\det Q)^{\frac{-n-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} (-\log(\det Q) + \alpha \log \det [I_n + \beta \hat{f}(Q)])} \\ &\propto \int_{D_N^{(Q)}} dQ (\det Q)^{\frac{-n-1}{2}} e^{-\frac{N}{2} (-\log(\det Q) + \alpha \log \det [I_n + \beta (Q + \sigma^2 E_n)])} \end{aligned} \quad (2.62)$$

Here, $\alpha = \frac{M}{N}$, ,

$\hat{f}(Q) = (Q + \sigma^2 E_n)$, and,
 E_n is an all 1's matrix

The asymptotic evaluation of 2.62 through Laplace's method for large $N \gg 1$ requires observation of $\Phi_n(Q)$ and its extrema ($\Phi_n(Q_{extr})$).

$$\Phi_n(Q) = (-\log(\det Q) + \alpha \log \det [I_n + \beta (Q + \sigma^2 E_n)]) \quad (2.63)$$

$$\langle Z^n \rangle_{\infty} e^{-\frac{N}{2}\Phi_n(Q_{extr})} \quad (2.64)$$

Using 2.64 in 2.43 we arrive at,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle \varepsilon_{min} \rangle}{N} = \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\beta} \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{n} \Phi_n(Q_{extr}) \quad (2.65)$$

2.3.3 Stationarity Conditions

To minimize $\Phi_n(Q)$, the stationarity conditions need to be solved for Q_{extr} leading to following conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Phi_n(Q)}{\partial Q_{ab}} &= 0, \forall a < b \\ \alpha (Q + \sigma^2 E_n)^{-1} \beta - (Q)_{ab}^{-1} &= 0 \\ (Q^{-1})_{ab} &= \alpha \beta (I_n + \beta (Q + \sigma^2 E_n))^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.66)$$

Using Replica symmetry ansatz[36], Q is assumed to be of the following form:

- All non-diagonal entries $Q_{ab} = q$, $\forall a \neq b$, such that $0 \leq q < 1$
- All diagonal entries $Q_{aa} = 1$, $\forall a$

Note that the matrix $R = I_n + \beta (Q + \sigma^2 E_n)$ is also of similar form with diagonal entries $r_d = 1 + \beta(1 + \sigma^2)$ and off diagonal entries $r = \beta(q + \sigma^2)$. For matrices such as Q and R the inverse and determinant are well known. The inverse and determinant of Q as presented in [23] without an explanation/formula for general matrix of such format are shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} (Q^{-1})_{aa} &= \frac{(1 + q(n - 2))}{(1 - q)(1 + q(n - 1))}, \\ (Q^{-1})_{a < b} &= -\frac{q}{(1 - q)(1 + q(n - 1))}, \\ \det Q &= (1 + q(n - 1))(1 - q)^{n-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.67)$$

Since R is of the same format of Q except that the entries differ, the inverse of R can be written in terms of r_d and r as shown below [49]. These also serve as generic formulae which can be used to arrive at the expressions in 2.67 of Q.

$$(R^{-1})_{aa} = \frac{r_d + r(n - 2)}{(r_d - r)(r_d - r(n - 1))}, \quad (R^{-1})_{a < b} = -\frac{r}{(r_d - r)(r_d - r(n - 1))},$$

I have presented the general determinant formula of R in terms of r_d and r as well. Again, note that the same formula is applied in case of Q as well to arrive at the result in 2.67.

$$\det R = (r_d + r(n - 1))(r_d - r)^{n-1}$$

Finally, by substituting the diagonal entries $r_d = 1 + \beta(1 + \sigma^2)$ and off diagonal entries $r = \beta(q + \sigma^2)$ in the above formulae, we arrive at the following

expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} (R^{-1})_{aa} &= \frac{(1 + \beta(1 + \sigma^2)) + \beta(q + \sigma^2)(n - 2)}{(1 + \beta(1 - q))(1 + \beta(1 + \sigma^2) + \beta(q + \sigma^2)(n - 1))}, \\ (R^{-1})_{a < b} &= -\frac{\beta(q + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \beta(1 - q))(1 + \beta(1 - q) + n\beta(q + \sigma^2))}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.68)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \det R &= (1 + \beta(1 + \sigma^2) + \beta(q + \sigma^2)(n - 1))(1 + \beta(1 - q))^{n-1} \\ &= \left(1 + \beta \left(1 + \frac{n\beta(q + \sigma^2)}{1 + \beta(1 - q)}\right)\right) (1 + \beta(1 - q))^n \end{aligned} \quad (2.69)$$

Using 2.67 and 2.68, the stationarity conditions 2.66 can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned} (Q^{-1})_{a < b} &= \alpha\beta (R^{-1})_{a < b} \\ \frac{q}{(1 - q)(1 + q(n - 1))} &= \alpha\beta \frac{\beta(q + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \beta - \beta q)(1 + \beta - \beta q + n\beta(q + \sigma^2))} \end{aligned}$$

At the limit of $n \rightarrow 0$,

$$\frac{q}{(1 - q)^2} = \alpha \frac{\beta^2(q + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \beta(1 - q))^2} \quad (2.70)$$

within the same replica symmetry ansatz, using 2.67 and 2.69, $\Phi_n(Q)$ in 2.63 can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_n(Q) &= \alpha \log \det R - \log \det Q \\ &= \alpha \left[\log(1 + \beta(1 - q))^n + \log \left[1 + \frac{n\beta(q + \sigma^2)}{1 + \beta(1 - q)} \right] \right] - \log[1 + q(n - 1)] - \log[1 - q]^{n-1} \\ \Phi_n(Q) &= \alpha n [\log(1 + \beta(1 - q))] + \alpha \log \left[1 + \frac{n\beta(q + \sigma^2)}{1 + \beta(1 - q)} \right] \\ &\quad - \log \left[1 + \frac{nq}{1 - q} \right] - n \log[1 - q] \end{aligned} \quad (2.71)$$

Since we are ultimately interested in $n \rightarrow 0$ limit,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{n} \Phi_n(Q) &= \alpha [\log(1 + \beta(1 - q))] + \frac{\alpha\beta(q + \sigma^2)}{1 + \beta(1 - q)} \\ &\quad - \frac{q}{1 - q} - \log(1 - q) \end{aligned} \quad (2.72)$$

2.3.4 Large deviation rate and minimal cost

The final step in recovering expected minimal cost and large deviation rate hinges upon our ability to analyse the derived expression for minimal cost in 2.65 in β space given the value of q , with in the replica symmetry ansatz $0 \leq q < 1$. At finite β , 2.70 is a cubic equation which can be solved for q . But our interest is in the limit of $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ to recover expected minimal cost. In the limit of $\beta \rightarrow \infty$, q can be,

- **non-negative and less than unity ($0 \leq q < 1$):**

using 2.65 and 2.72,

$$\beta \rightarrow \infty \text{ and } 0 \leq q < 1 \implies \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\langle \varepsilon_{min} \rangle}{N} = 0$$

Further probing into the values of q for which the above holds true by applying the $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ on stationarity condition in 2.70 results in,

$$\begin{aligned} q &= \alpha(q + \sigma^2) \\ q(1 - \alpha) &= \alpha\sigma^2 \\ q &= \frac{\alpha\sigma^2}{1 - \alpha} \\ \because 0 &\leq q < 1, \text{ using above expression for } q, \\ 0 &\leq \frac{\alpha\sigma^2}{1 - \alpha} < 1 \\ 0 &\leq \alpha\sigma^2 < 1 - \alpha \\ 0 &\leq \sigma^2 < \frac{1}{\alpha} - 1 \\ 1 &\leq 1 + \sigma^2 < \frac{1}{\alpha} \\ 1 &\geq \frac{1}{1 + \sigma^2} < \alpha \\ \because \alpha &= \frac{M}{N} > 0, \\ 0 &< \alpha < \frac{1}{1 + \sigma^2} \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

$\alpha_c = \frac{1}{1 + \sigma^2}$ is a compatibility threshold under which, system is compatible hence the above observed result of vanishing cost.

- **can tend to unity such that $\beta(1 - q)$ in the denominator of 2.70 is finite:**

For $\alpha > \alpha_c$, the cost is positive for a finite $\nu = \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \beta(1 - q)$ implying the incompatibility of the system of equations on a sphere.

In the case of non-zero positive cost ($\alpha > \alpha_c$), the large deviation function can be recovered by finding $\phi(s)$. By comparison of 2.47 and 2.64, $\phi(s)$ can be found as:

$$\phi(s) = -\frac{1}{2} \lim_{\substack{n=s/\beta \\ \beta \rightarrow \infty}} \Phi_n(Q_{extr})$$

Substituting $n = \frac{s}{\beta}$ and $q = 1 - \frac{\nu}{\beta}$ in 2.71 and evaluating the resultant function at $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ gives rise to the following functional $\Phi(s, \nu)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi(s, \nu) &= \lim_{\substack{n=s/\beta \\ q=1-\frac{\nu}{\beta} \\ \beta \rightarrow \infty}} \Phi_n(Q) \\ &= \lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \left[\alpha \frac{s}{\beta} [\log(1 + \nu)] + \alpha \log \left[1 + \frac{s(1 - \frac{\nu}{\beta} + \sigma^2)}{1 + \nu} \right] - \log \left[1 + \frac{s(\beta - \nu)}{\nu\beta} \right] - \frac{s}{\beta} \log \left[\frac{\nu}{\beta} \right] \right] \\ &\implies \Phi(s, \nu) = \alpha \log \left[1 + \frac{s(1 + \sigma^2)}{1 + \nu} \right] - \log \left[1 + \frac{s}{\nu} \right] \quad (2.73) \end{aligned}$$

From stationarity condition,

$$\lim_{\substack{n=s/\beta \\ q=1-\frac{\nu}{\beta} \\ \beta \rightarrow \infty}} \left[\frac{q}{(1-q)(1+q(n-1))} = \alpha\beta \frac{\beta(q+\sigma^2)}{(1+\beta-\beta q)(1+\beta-\beta q+n\beta(q+\sigma^2))} \right]$$

$$\lim_{\beta \rightarrow \infty} \left[\frac{1-\frac{\nu}{\beta}}{\nu \left[s + \nu - \frac{\nu s}{\beta} \right]} = \alpha \frac{1-\frac{\nu}{\beta} + \sigma^2}{(1+\nu) \left(1 + \nu + s \left(1 - \frac{\nu}{\beta} + \sigma^2 \right) \right)} \right]$$

$$\frac{1}{\nu[s+\nu]} = \frac{\alpha(1+\sigma^2)}{(1+\nu)(1+\nu+s(1+\sigma^2))} \quad (2.74)$$

$$\implies \phi(s) = -\frac{1}{2}\Phi(s, \nu(s)) \quad (2.75)$$

where $\nu(s)$ is the solution of ν in 2.74

Finally, following 2.48 the Legendre transformation over the variable s results in Large deviation rate as shown below.

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{e}) = -(\mathbf{e}s_* + \phi(s_*))$$

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{e}) = \frac{1}{2}(\Phi(s_*, \nu(s_*)) - 2\mathbf{e}s_*) \quad (2.76)$$

where s_* is found using 2.48 by solving the following equation:

$$\mathbf{e} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{d\Phi}{ds} \Big|_{s_*}$$

$$\because \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \Phi(s, v) = 0,$$

$$\mathbf{e} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \Phi(s, v)}{\partial s} \Big|_{s_*}$$

Using the expression of $\Phi(s, \nu)$ from 2.73 for necessary differentiation followed by using the stationarity condition 2.74,

$$\mathbf{e} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha(1+\sigma^2)}{1+\nu+s_*(1+\sigma^2)} - \frac{1}{\nu+s_*} \right) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1+\nu}{\nu(\nu+s_*)} - \frac{1}{\nu+s_*} \right) = \frac{1}{2\nu(\nu+s_*)}$$

$$\implies \nu(\nu+s_*) = \frac{1}{2\mathbf{e}} \quad (2.77)$$

Using the stationarity condition 2.74,

$$\frac{1}{\nu[s_*+\nu]} = \frac{\alpha(1+\sigma^2)}{(1+\nu)(1+\nu+s_*(1+\sigma^2))}$$

$$\nu[s_*+\nu]\alpha(1+\sigma^2) = (1+\nu)(1+\nu+s_*(1+\sigma^2))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(1 - \alpha\nu + \nu)s_*(1 + \sigma^2) &= -(1 + \nu)^2 + \nu^2\alpha(1 + \sigma^2) \\
(1 - \nu(\alpha - 1))s_*(1 + \sigma^2) &= \nu^2(\alpha(1 + \sigma^2) - 1) - 2\nu - 1 \\
\implies s_*(1 + \sigma^2) &= \frac{\nu^2(\alpha(1 + \sigma^2) - 1) - 2\nu - 1}{(1 - \nu(\alpha - 1))} \quad (2.78)
\end{aligned}$$

Substituting 2.77 and 2.78 in 2.74 gives,

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)\frac{1}{2e} &= (1 + \nu) \left(1 + \nu + \frac{\nu^2(\alpha(1 + \sigma^2) - 1) - 2\nu - 1}{(1 - \nu(\alpha - 1))} \right) \\
&= \frac{(1 + \nu)(1 - \nu(\alpha - 1)) + \nu^2\alpha + \nu^2\alpha\sigma^2 - \nu^2 - 2\nu - 1}{(1 - \nu(\alpha - 1))} \\
&= \frac{(1 + \nu)^2 - \nu\alpha + \nu^2\alpha\sigma^2 - (1 + \nu)^2}{(1 - \nu(\alpha - 1))} \\
&= \frac{\alpha(1 + \nu)(\nu\sigma^2 - 1)\nu}{1 - \nu(\alpha - 1)} \\
\implies \sigma^2\nu^3 + \nu^2(\sigma^2 - 1) - \nu(1 - \alpha(\alpha - 1)) - \alpha &= 0, \quad a := \frac{1 + \sigma^2}{2e} \quad (2.79)
\end{aligned}$$

This is a closed form equation solved for ν for a given e showing that the knowledge of ν is enough for recovering large deviation rate as detailed below. Using 2.74 and re-writing the equation as,

$$\left(\frac{1 + \nu + s(1 + \sigma^2)}{1 + \nu} \right) = \left(\frac{\nu(\nu + s)}{(1 + \nu)^2} \alpha (1 + \sigma^2) \right)$$

Applying logarithm on both sides and multiplying by α gives the following identity,

$$\alpha \log \left(\frac{1 + \nu + s(1 + \sigma^2)}{1 + \nu} \right) = \alpha \log \left(\frac{\nu(\nu + s)}{(1 + \nu)^2} \alpha (1 + \sigma^2) \right)$$

Using this identity in 2.73 gives,

$$\begin{aligned}
\Phi(s, \nu) &= \alpha \log \left(\frac{\nu(\nu + s)\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \nu)^2} \right) - \log \left[1 + \frac{s}{\nu} \right] \\
&= \alpha \log \left(\frac{\nu(\nu + s)\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \nu)^2} \right) - \log \left[\frac{(\nu + s)\nu}{\nu^2} \right] \\
\implies \Phi(s, \nu) &= \alpha \log \left(\frac{\nu(\nu + s)\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \nu)^2} \right) - \log [(\nu + s)\nu] + 2 \log \nu \quad (2.80)
\end{aligned}$$

By substituting 2.77 in 2.80 we can write $\Phi(s, \nu)$ as $\Phi(e, \nu)$ as shown below.

$$\Phi(e, \nu) = \alpha \log \left(\frac{\frac{1}{2e}\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)}{(1 + \nu)^2} \right) - \log \left[\frac{1}{2e} \right] + 2 \log \nu$$

$$\begin{aligned} \implies \Phi(e, \nu) &= -(\alpha - 1) \log(2e) + \alpha \log(\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)) \\ &\quad + 2 \log \nu - 2\alpha \log(1 + \nu) \end{aligned} \quad (2.81)$$

Using 2.76, 2.77, and 2.79,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(e) &= \frac{1}{2}(\Phi(s_*, \nu(s_*)) - 2es_*) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\Phi(e, \nu) - \frac{1}{\nu} - 2e\nu) \\ \implies \mathcal{L}(e) &= e\nu - \frac{1}{2\nu} - \frac{\alpha - 1}{2} \log(2e) + \frac{\alpha}{2} \log(\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)) \\ &\quad + \log \nu - \alpha \log(1 + \nu) \end{aligned} \quad (2.82)$$

Here ν for a given value of e is the solution of equation 2.79 and the equation 2.82 gives the large deviation rate for the associated $(\nu(e), e)$. The value of e that minimizes $\mathcal{L}(e)$ is the minimal cost. Note that for the value $e_* := \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{\alpha(1 + \sigma^2)} - 1 \right)^2$ [23] the solution of the cubic equation 2.79 is $\nu_* := 1/\sqrt{2e_*}$ and $\mathcal{L}(e) = 0$ validating the derivation of expected minimal cost by Lagrange multiplier method. The following simulation of the random minimization of the least square cost function using Riemannian optimization on spherical manifold further validates the expected minimal cost and large deviation rate of the expected minimal cost derived using statistical mechanics approach.

Figure 2.8: e_{min} from simulation

Figure 2.9: large deviation rate of e_{min} from simulation(LDR sim) vs analytical(LDR)

2.4 Comparison and tuning of search algorithms

It is possible to solve the current optimization problem by other algorithms without explicitly resorting to optimization on the spherical manifold as detailed in 2.1. A simple gradient descent [38] algorithm is an obvious choice as the gradient can be evaluated. Since the gradient is available the simulated annealing of Langevin dynamics [8] is an appropriate method of optimization as well. Finally, the problem of solving the system of linear equations can also be mapped to neural network architecture [30][15]. Though the spherical manifold is not explicitly considered in intermediate steps of typical implementations of the above algorithms, I have implemented in such a way that the updated position in ambient space is retracted onto the sphere with all the above approaches.

2.4.1 Gradient descent

The gradient descent approach is an iterative algorithm with the updation of parameters along a new search direction dictated by the steepest descent of the cost at each iteration. A constant step size along the search direction, given by the gradient of the cost function, is computationally efficient as opposed to line search with variable step sizes at each iteration. The gradient descent algorithm with a tunable hyperparameter γ is listed below.

<p>Initialize x_0, max.iterations and step size γ :</p> <p>Calculate Euclidean gradient $\Delta H(x)$</p> $x_{new} = x_{old} - \gamma \Delta H(x)$ $x_{new}^{retracted} = \frac{x_{new}}{\ x_{new}\ }$ <p>iterate until convergence($\Delta H(x) < \varepsilon$)/max.iterations</p>	(2.83)
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I have implemented the above algorithm for least square cost minimization on the sphere in Python as shown below. The simulation for many random instances of A and b is performed as shown in 2.1 except that the optimization algorithm is switched to gradient descent.

```

1 # Function to calculate the least square cost
2 def least_square_cost(X, A, b):
3     X=X.reshape([N,1])
4     return np.linalg.norm(A@X - b)**2
5 # Gradient of the least square cost function
6 def gradient_least_square(X, A, b):
7     X=X.reshape([N,1])
8     residual = (A@X) - b
9     gradient = 2 * A.T @residual
10    gradient=gradient.reshape([N,1])
11    return gradient
12 #update
13 def gradient_based_local_search(X, A, b, step_size):
14    X=X.reshape([N,1])
15    gradient = gradient_least_square(X, A, b)

```

```

16     gradient=gradient.reshape([N,1])
17     neighbor_solution = X.reshape([N,1]) - step_size * gradient
18     neighbor_solution=neighbor_solution.reshape([N,1])
19     return neighbor_solution
20 # Gradient descent
21 def simple_gradient(mu,sigma,M,N, max_iterations, step_size):
22     # Generate random matrix A from a Gaussian distribution
23     for i in range(1000):
24         A = np.matrix(mu+1*np.random.standard_normal(size=(M,N))).
25         reshape((M,N))
26         W=A@A.T
27         is_positive_definite = np.all(np.isreal(np.linalg.eigvals(W
28         )))and np.all(np.linalg.eigvals(W) > 0)
29         if is_positive_definite:
30             """print ('found W')"""
31             break
32     # Generate random matrices b from a Gaussian distribution
33     e = np.random.standard_normal(size=M)
34     b=np.matrix(mu+sigma*e).reshape((M,1))
35     e = np.matrix(e).reshape((M,1))
36
37     final_cost=0
38     final_solution=0
39     for i in range (10):
40         #initialize x on sphere
41         initial_X = np.random.randn(N)
42         initial_solution=initial_X/np.linalg.norm(initial_X)
43
44         current_solution = initial_solution
45
46         for iteration in range(max_iterations):
47             # Generate neighboring solution using gradient-based
48             local search
49             neighbor_solution = gradient_based_local_search(
50             current_solution, A, b, step_size)
51             #Retraction onto the sphere
52             neighbor_solution=neighbor_solution/np.linalg.norm(
53             neighbor_solution)
54
55             # Evaluate cost functions
56             current_cost = least_square_cost(current_solution, A, b
57             )
58             neighbor_cost = least_square_cost(neighbor_solution, A,
59             b)
60
61             # Calculate the change in cost
62             delta_cost = neighbor_cost - current_cost
63
64             # Accept or reject the neighbor
65             if delta_cost < 0 :
66                 current_solution = neighbor_solution
67                 current_cost=neighbor_cost
68
69             if i==0:
70                 final_solution=current_solution
71                 final_cost=current_cost
72             else:
73                 delta_cost = current_cost - final_cost
74                 # Accept or reject the neighbor
75                 if delta_cost < 0 :
76                     final_solution = current_solution
77                     final_cost=current_cost

```

```

71     lambda_min=np.average(-(A.T @ b - (A.T @ A) @
72     final_solution)/final_solution)/N
73     emin=least_square_cost(final_solution, A, b)/(2*N)
74     #Flag for negative Lagrange multiplier
75     if lambda_min<0:
76         n_lg_counter=1
77     else:
78         n_lg_counter=0
79
80     return [n_lg_counter, lambda_min, emin]

```

Listing 2.3: Gradient descent with retraction onto sphere

2.4.2 Metropolis Adjusted Langevin

The least-square cost minimization on a sphere can be solved in approaches inspired by molecular simulations with hill-climbing heuristics. The approach renders itself useful in climbing energy barriers. In the optimization context, the energy is the cost function, and, the hill-climbing ability is the algorithmic efficiency in reaching the global minimum by climbing out of the local minimum in non-convex problems with multiple local minima. The Langevin dynamics is one such approach inspired by physical simulations [8]. The stochastic algorithm of Langevin dynamics ($x_{new} = x_{old} - \gamma \Delta H(x) + \sqrt{2T\gamma} \varepsilon$), [11][43][26], helps avoid local minima and ensures convergence to stationary distribution. However, a sampling procedure such as MCMC (Monte Carlo Markov chain) helps in convergence to target distribution.

The simulated annealing methodology is borrowed from annealing in computational physics, and, it is introduced with MCMC procedure to sample from Gibbs Boltzmann target distribution [31]. But it can be used in conjunction with Langevin dynamics as well [43][26]. The probability density of x is assumed to be of Gibbs Boltzmann type with cost function $H(X)$ serving as the Hamiltonian/energy function, and, it is proportional to $e^{-\beta H(x)}$ where β is inverse temperature [11]. The MCMC procedure constructs a stochastic Markov chain, via update rule and acceptance criterion, that satisfies ergodicity and detailed balance conditions ensuring the convergence to the equilibrium distribution of Gibbs Boltzmann type. The transition probability between two states or an update only depends on the difference between the energies of the two states. However, the usual update procedure of MCMC is exhaustive (global) and only depends on the energy which can result in high computational cost and slow convergence in high dimensional space. On the other hand, guidance of the gradient of energy, as in Langevin dynamics, is promising in shortening simulation length. The combination of Langevin dynamics for gradient-guided update rule and metropolis acceptance criterion for the update possesses the advantages of both procedures [11]. This is usually referred to as Metropolis adjusted Langevin algorithm (MALA) [34]. The MALA algorithm is as shown below:

Initialize x_0 , step size (γ) schedule, Temperature(T) schedule,
and max.iterations:
Calculate Euclidean gradient $\Delta H(x)$
 $\varepsilon \sim N(0,1)$
Langevin Dynamics: $\hat{x}_{new} = x_{old} - \gamma \Delta H(x) + \sqrt{2T\gamma} \varepsilon$

$$\hat{x}_{new}^{retracted} = \frac{\hat{x}_{new}}{\|\hat{x}_{new}\|}$$
Metropolis Acceptance criterion = $e^{\beta(H(x_{old}) - H(\hat{x}_{new}^{retracted}))}$ (2.84)
Acceptance probability $p_{acc} = \min(1, e^{\beta(H(x_{old}) - H(\hat{x}_{new}^{retracted}))})$
if $p_{acc} > \text{Rand} \sim \text{Uniform}(0,1)$:
Accept: $x_{new} = \hat{x}_{new}^{retracted}$
else:
Reject: $x_{new} = x_{old}$
iterate until convergence($\Delta H(x) < \varepsilon$)/max.iterations

The simulated annealing involves slow cooling meaning a gradual reduction of temperature while simulation to ensure convergence to the global minimum. The choice of method for scheduling temperature and step size changes over the iterations can vary but I have found that an equally spaced sample from a specific range is sufficient in the present case. The range still needs to be specified and tuned for optimality. I have implemented the algorithm in 2.84 in python as shown below and the simulation for random instances of A and b is performed as specified in 2.1.

```

1 #loss
2 def loss_function(x, A, b):
3     return np.linalg.norm(A @ x - b)**2
4 #gradient
5 def gradient(x, A, b):
6     return 2*A.T @ (A @ x - b)
7 #retraction
8 def project_onto_sphere(x):
9     norm_x = np.linalg.norm(x)
10    return x / norm_x
11 #MALA update
12 def mala_update(x, step_size, temperature, A, b):
13    gradient_H = gradient(x, A, b)#(np.identity(N)-x@x.T)*
14    xi = np.sqrt(2 * step_size * temperature)*np.random.normal(0,
15    1, size=len(x))
16    proposal = x - step_size * gradient_H+xi.reshape((N,1))
17    proposed_on_sphere = project_onto_sphere(proposal)
18    # Metropolis acceptance probability
19    current_H = loss_function(x, A, b)
20    proposed_H = loss_function(proposed_on_sphere, A, b)
21    acceptance_prob = min(1, np.exp((current_H - proposed_H) /
22    temperature))
23    delta_c=(current_H - proposed_H)
24    # Accept or reject move
25    if delta_c>0 or np.random.rand() < acceptance_prob:
26        return proposed_on_sphere
27    else:

```

```

26     return x
27 def simulated_annealing_MALA( mu,sigma,M,N,step_size_schedule ,
    temperature_schedule , max_iterations):
28
29     initial_X = np.random.randn(N)
30     x=initial_X/np.linalg.norm(initial_X)
31     x=x.reshape([N,1])
32     # Generate random matrix A from a Gaussian distribution
33     for i in range(1000):
34         A = np.matrix(mu+1*np.random.standard_normal(size=(M,N))).
    reshape((M,N))
35         W=A@A.T
36         is_positive_definite = np.all(np.isreal(np.linalg.eigvals(W
    )))and np.all(np.linalg.eigvals(W) > 0)
37         if is_positive_definite:
38             """print ('found W')"""
39             break
40     # Generate random matrices b from a Gaussian distribution
41     e = np.random.standard_normal(size=M)
42     b=np.matrix(mu+sigma*e).reshape((M,1))
43     e = np.matrix(e).reshape((M,1))
44
45
46     final_solution=0
47     final_cost=0
48
49     for iteration in range(max_iterations):
50         epsilon = step_size_schedule[iteration]
51         temperature = temperature_schedule[iteration]
52         x = mala_update(x, epsilon, temperature, A, b)
53         current_solution=x
54         current_cost=loss_function(x,A,b)
55
56         if iteration==0:
57             final_solution=current_solution
58             final_cost=current_cost
59         else:
60             if current_cost<final_cost:
61                 final_cost=current_cost
62                 final_solution=current_solution
63             else:
64                 final_cost=final_cost
65                 final_solution=final_solution
66
67         lambda_min=np.average(-(A.T @ b - (A.T @ A) @ final_solution)/
    final_solution)/N
68         emin=loss_function(final_solution, A, b)/(2*N)
69         #Flag for negative Lagrange multiplier
70         if lambda_min<0:
71             n_lg_counter=1
72         else:
73             n_lg_counter=0
74
75     return [n_lg_counter , lambda_min , emin]

```

Listing 2.4: Metropolis adjusted langevin algorithm with retraction onto sphere

2.4.3 Neural Networks

Finally, I considered the neural network approach to the optimization problem. A Neural network is a combination of multiple neurons distributed across sev-

eral layers with interconnections between layers [28]. The data is processed in the forward direction, thus named the feed-forward networks, and, the error is back-propagated [42]. At each neuron, a linear combination of the incoming multiple data points and a set of weights is computed, and, passed to a linear/non-linear activation function. The output of the activation function is then passed onto further layers. The back-propagation of error is for updating the parameters or weights of the neural network using gradient descent by decomposing the overall gradient of the error into individual contributions from parameters at each neuron across different layers. The decomposition of the gradient is achieved by the chain rule of calculus, starting from the output layer and moving backward in the network, and, the gradient of error function with respect to parameters at each layer is utilized to update the parameters in the direction of steepest descent of the error. The nature of the activation functions and the connecting architecture significantly influence error minimizing process. So, they need to be chosen appropriately depending on the complexity of the input-output relationship.

The suitability of Neural networks for solving systems of linear equations is well studied [15][30]. In the present case, the x that minimizes the least square cost needs to be solved. The neural network approximates the candidate $\phi(\theta)$ for x where θ are the parameters or weights of the network. The back-propagation of mean squared error $\frac{1}{M} \|A\phi(\theta) - b\|^2$ enables such approximation. The choice of the number of hidden layers, the number of neurons in the hidden layers, and, the activation functions at neurons is yet to be made. The gradient descent algorithm for neural network solving system of linear equations is shown below:

Initialize θ , learning rate τ and number of epochs:

Calculate the loss: $\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \frac{1}{M} \|A\phi(\theta) - b\|^2 = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M (a_k \phi(\theta) - b_k)^2$

Calculate the gradient: $\Delta_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta) = \frac{2}{M} \sum_{k=1}^M (a_k \phi(\theta) - b_k)^2 a_k \mathcal{J}(\phi(\theta))$ (2.85)

, $\mathcal{J}(\phi(\theta))$ is the derivative of the active function with respect to θ

Update parameters $\theta_{new} = \theta_{old} - \tau \Delta_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta)$
iterate until convergence

In the present case, I have found that a fully connected neural network with a dense layer with one neuron is sufficient to solve for x . The weights of the densely connected neuron are considered as the candidate for x . Also, no activation function is used which is equivalent to a linear activation function $mx + c$ where c is zero and m is 1. The spherical constraint is dealt with by setting kernel constraint to the unit norm. This leaves out only one hyper-parameter to be chosen and tuned yet, i.e., learning rate τ . In such a setting it is obvious that the neural network output is equivalent to $a_k x$, and, given b is used for loss calculation and back-propagation. I have implemented the algorithm in 2.85 with the above configuration using the Tensorflow implementation of learning on neural network architecture as shown below.

```
1 # Define the neural network model
```

```

2 def minimization_model(input_size, x_init):
3     model = tf.keras.Sequential()
4     custom_init_values = x_init.astype(np.float32)
5     #Dense layer with 1 neuron
6     model.add(tf.keras.layers.Dense(1, use_bias=False,
7         kernel_initializer=tf.constant_initializer(custom_init_values),
8         kernel_constraint=tf.keras.constraints.unit_norm()))
9     return model
10 # Training loop
11 def train_minimization_model(model, input_data, target, epochs,
12     learning_rate):
13     lr_schedule = tf.keras.optimizers.schedules.ExponentialDecay(
14         learning_rate, decay_steps=epochs, decay_rate=1, staircase=True
15     )
16     optimizer = tf.optimizers.Adam(learning_rate=lr_schedule)
17
18     for epoch in range(epochs):
19         with tf.GradientTape() as tape:
20             prediction = model(input_data)
21             loss = loss_function(prediction, target)
22
23             gradients = tape.gradient(loss, model.trainable_variables)
24             optimizer.apply_gradients(zip(gradients, model.
25                 trainable_variables))
26 #Loss
27 def loss_function(prediction, target):
28     mse_loss = tf.keras.losses.MeanSquaredError()(prediction,
29         target)
30     return mse_loss
31 # Generate random matrix A from a Gaussian distribution
32 for i in range(1000):
33     A = np.matrix(mu+1*np.random.standard_normal(size=(M,N))).
34         reshape((M,N))
35     W=A@A.T
36     is_positive_definite = np.all(np.isreal(np.linalg.eigvals(W)))
37     and np.all(np.linalg.eigvals(W) > 0)
38     if is_positive_definite:
39         """print ('found W')"""
40         break
41 # Generate random matrices b from a Gaussian distribution
42 e = np.random.standard_normal(size=M)
43 b=np.matrix(mu+sigma*e).reshape((M,1))
44 e = np.matrix(e).reshape((M,1))
45
46 #neural network for system of linear equations
47 def nn_opt(A,b,learning_rate,epochs):
48     A2 = tf.constant(A, dtype=tf.float32)
49     b2 = tf.constant(b, dtype=tf.float32)
50     x_init=np.random.randn(N)
51     x_init=x_init/np.linalg.norm(x_init)
52     learning_rate=learning_rate
53     # Define the loss function
54
55     # Create and train the model with multiple dense layers
56     input_size = A.shape[1]
57     model = minimization_model(input_size,x_init )
58     train_minimization_model(model, A2, b2,epochs,learning_rate)
59     x_result=model.layers[-1].kernel.numpy()
60     Xopt_point2=x_result
61     A=np.matrix(A)
62     b=np.matrix(b)

```

```

56     lambda_min=np.average(-(A.T @ b - (A.T @ A) @ x_result)/
57     x_result)/N
58     e_min=(np.linalg.norm(A@model.layers[-1].kernel.numpy()-b)**2)
59     / (2*N)
59     if lambda_min<0:
60         n_lg_counter=1
61     else:
62         n_lg_counter=0
63
64
65     return [n_lg_counter,lambda_min,e_min]

```

Listing 2.5: Neural network with retraction onto sphere

2.4.4 Results

Since we know the expected minimal cost and the large deviation rate of the random optimization landscape, the search strategies of different algorithms can be informed, and the results can be compared to assess the reliability of an algorithm in converging to the global minimum. The first can be accomplished by hyper-parameter tuning for comparable results ($\langle e_{min} \rangle - opt(e_{min}) < \epsilon$) and the later can be achieved by comparing the large deviation rate from simulations to that of its theoretical counterpart. The hyper-parameters of the algorithms 2.83, 2.84, and, 2.85 tuned to produce comparable results are shown in table 2.1. For a system configuration : ($N = 50, M = 75, \sigma = 0.5, \alpha = 1.5$), the compari-

Gradient-Descent	Metropolis Adjusted Langevin	Neural Network
$\gamma = 0.001$	γ schedule= np.linspace(.001,.00085,max.iter)	$\tau = 0.01$
max.iterations=300	T schedule= np.linspace($\frac{1}{N}, \frac{1}{2N}, max.iter$)	epochs=200
multi.start=10	max.iterations=300	Architecture: 1 Dense layer with 1 neuron, and, Kernel constraint of unit norm

Table 2.1: Hyper parameter configuration

son of minimal cost achieved by the above three algorithms after tuning along with the Reimaniann conjugate gradient descent discussed in 2.1 in 10000 runs with the expected minimal cost can be observed in figure 2.10. It is evident that the results are comparable and all the peaks of respective histograms of minimal cost point to the expected minimal cost. For the same system configuration and algorithms, the large deviation rate computed from the probability distribution of minimal cost from 10000 samples is compared with that of theoretically derived results. The run time comparison is presented in Figure.2.2. The large deviation rate from the simulation of all algorithms, as observed in figure 2.11, reasonably reproduces results derived in 2.3.4. The complete collection of programming material will be shared at the GitHub repository linked here, [code repository].

n.sim	RCGD	GD	MALA	NN
1	0.1007 s	0.4603 s	0.0327 s	1.2592 s
10000	16.78 min	1.27 hr	5.45 min	3.47 hr

Table 2.2: Run time(fixed $\sigma, N=50, M=75$) \sim RCGD:Reimannian Conjugate gradient descent, GD: Gradient Descent, MALA: Metropolis Adjusted Langevin Algorithm, NN: Neural Network

Figure 2.10: e_{min} from simulation

Figure 2.11: Large deviation rate from simulation

Conclusion and prospective directions

This thesis covers a coherent and detailed picture of the random least square optimization landscape with a spherical constraint, including sufficient background literature. A mathematically thorough approach, combining a Kac-Rice approach with the Random Matrix Theory of the Wishart ensemble, to recover statistics of minimal cost is explicated. In contrast, a hypothesis-driven statistical mechanics approach, the Replica trick, catering to similar endeavors is elucidated. The analytical derivations of statistics of minimal cost such as normalized asymptotic mean minimal cost, associated minimal Lagrange multiplier, and respective large deviation rate from both the approaches are not only presented in detail but are reproduced numerically by four different gradient-based algorithmic approaches namely Riemannian conjugate gradient descent, simple gradient descent, Metropolis adjusted Langevin, and, gradient descent on a neural network with backpropagation. These algorithms are implemented with necessary modifications to fit the current problem. The agreement of results among both the theoretical approaches added confidence to the derived results. The convergence of numerical simulations to that of theoretical results further verified the veracity of the theoretical results, and, allowed for comparison among different algorithmic approaches to the current optimization problem. To that end, this thesis also covered the machinery and flexibility available, such as hyper-parameter tuning, in each of the algorithmic approaches to accurately infer the solution to the optimization problem.

The plausibilities of extension to the work in this thesis are multi-fold. Building rigorous theory for optimization problems with more complex cost functions or constraint spaces by mounting on the core methodologies and techniques used in the current analytical work is a natural direction to extend research. Working with random quadratic equations on a sphere is one such example and working with complex non-euclidean manifolds other than a sphere is another such example where new challenges arise due to the problem of finding appropriate Riemannian metric tensors. Though quantification of uncertainty corresponding to minimal cost is achieved through the large deviation rate, the range of validity is still unclear. So, one could aim to fill the research gap in existing results. The other dimension is to extensively investigate or develop the literature on suitable algorithms for simulating optimization problems in such complex landscapes with or without well-defined costs or constraints. The

numerical results could catalyze theory development by building intuition in such cases where the problem is inaccessible to current theoretical tools. On the other hand, the computational cost, precision, advanced variants, and, limitations of the algorithmic approaches used in the current dissertation can be studied further in detail. The optimization problems with reasonably familiar landscapes, such as the current one, are a platform to benchmark and develop efficient search algorithms. Though the algorithms presented in this thesis show comparable results, the higher order approximations of Langevin dynamics and backpropagation, and, Riemannian manifold Langevin are few potential variants to study the current problem or a much more general optimization problem of our choice,[50][27][6]. Such an investigation could draw new insights and inspire interdisciplinary applications to real-world problems with similar characteristics to the constrained optimization profile studied in this dissertation.

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Self Assessment

Summary: The optimization landscape of the random least square cost function with spherical constraint is investigated via diverse approaches, specifically two different analytical approaches, accompanied by four different numerical approaches with the gradient descent principle at the core. The methodologies of Random Matrix Theory (RMT) combined with the Kac-Rice approach and the heuristic replica trick approach of statistical mechanics are explained, and, the analytical results of statistics of minimal cost such as mean and large deviation rate are presented. The details of the four algorithms, namely Gradient descent (GD), Riemannian GD, Metropolis Adjusted Langevin, and GD on the neural networks with backpropagation are presented and the relevant results are recovered from numerous simulations of the random minimization problem. The elucidation of various phenomena and the comparison of results is achieved with appropriate visualizations as well.

Scientific quality: In my assessment, the scientific quality of this thesis is notably high. The necessary background literature is presented in every section for objective and scientific reasoning. The analytical methods presented coherently are extremely detailed. Even the numerical exploratory analysis demonstrating topology trivialization, and, property relating minimum Lagrange multiplier with minimal cost are illustrated with appropriate visualizations. The algorithmic sections are also equally rigorous with sufficient background and all of them perform well in reproducing analytical results. Covering multiple algorithms not only validated analytical results but also showed potential for benchmarking for efficiency and reliability.

This thesis is largely self-sufficient although I would have liked to cover the background of Replica symmetry ansatz in section 2.3. Though the numerical results of statistics of minimal cost in sections 2.2.5, 2.3.4, and 2.4.4 are price enough, the number of simulations could have been higher for more precision. Finally, the derivations of the minimal Lagrange multiplier and cost could have been more explicit in section 2.3.4. However, I chose to skip simple algebraic steps, unlike with the other derivations with tricky manipulations and application of diverse mathematical concepts.

Breadth: A diverse range of topics are covered in this thesis. I have extensively read research papers beyond the original set of papers presented with the research topic, which is manifested in the references provided. I have covered a whole host of conceptual frameworks and algorithmic approaches to be able to present a coherent and complete picture of the random landscape under study. In addition to RMT with Kac-Rice and the Hamiltonian viewpoint of statisti-

cal mechanics, I have resorted to the optimization on the Riemannian manifold for non-euclidean spaces, Langevin dynamics for simulated annealing, and, the neural network with backpropagation, with the common principle of gradient descent to cover the numerical analysis. Since I have covered a variety of approaches, I could not go as extensively as I could in a few individual areas. For instance the reasoning behind the chosen hyperparameter configuration based on my analysis of sampling strategies of hyperparameter space and convergence rates of the algorithms.

Originality: Some of the approaches presented in this thesis are original, especially in the algorithmic sections. Though I have used an existing implementation of Riemannian gradient descent, I have presented the algorithm being used with a well-researched explanation rooted in Riemannian geometry. The combination of gradient-based Langevin dynamics with the Metropolis-Hastings approach with retraction of proposed solutions, in the direction of maximum descent, onto to sphere is a result of extensive research into algorithms and necessary modification suitable for the current problem. In addition to that, given the approaches are original with required modifications I have implemented all optimization approaches on my own in Python from scratch except the Riemannian approach and provided the full code base for scrutiny. Though the analytical derivations presented are not my own, I have studied them in depth during my thesis, and, filled in intermediate steps and sufficient reasoning on my own.

Presentation: The presentation is comprehensive and logical. All the sections are interdependent and they present a coherent narrative. The sections that follow expand on earlier sections with a logical flow. I have written a concise introduction followed by detailed analytical and numerical methodologies ending in a conclusion summarizing and providing prospective research direction. The Language used is intended to be unambiguous to the reader. In that effort, I had to resort to elaborate compound statements often and my writing could be improved in that sense. The mathematical elements are presented with meticulous detail to make the technical details accessible to readers with no familiarity with this topic. The visualizations are used effectively in exploration, for validation of assumptions and to showcase results. Finally, the code listings are provided in algorithmic approaches for clarity. On the whole, I believe the presentation is well crafted.